

BorderForce

Flexible system extending automated border surveillance by increased situational awareness adaptable to uncertain times with unforeseen events

D6.2 – Initial Communication, Dissemination, Advisory Board Activities and Exploitation/Standardisation Plan

WP6 - Initial Communication, Dissemination, Exploitation and Standardisation

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Publishable Executive Summary

Deliverable D6.2 – “Initial Communication, Dissemination, Advisory Board Activities and Exploitation/Standardisation Plan” is the second deliverable of WP6 – “Initial Communication, Dissemination, Exploitation and Standardisation,” within the BorderForce project. Coordinated by GSH and prepared in collaboration with AIT and ED, it covers the first 15 months of project activities (M1–M15) and builds upon the Initial Communication and Dissemination Plan established in Month 3.

The purpose of this deliverable is to provide a structured overview of the communication and dissemination activities carried out, the engagement with the Advisory Board and other stakeholders and the preliminary exploitation and standardisation plans.

Chapter 3 reports the actual communication and dissemination activities, including digital and print materials, website and social media presence, newsletters, press releases, videos, podcasts, articles, and participation in events. Monitoring and evaluation processes are also described to assess effectiveness and inform next steps.

Chapter 4 presents the Advisory Board activities and outreach to external stakeholders, including border authorities, official bodies and collaborations with other EU projects.

Chapter 5 outlines the exploitation plan, including key exploitable results, stakeholders and end-users, market analysis, SWOT assessment and preliminary route-to-market and distribution channels. Individual exploitation plans collected from project partners provide a baseline for Month 15, while expected short- and long-term impacts on society and stakeholders are discussed.

Chapter 6 presents the standardisation plan, detailing objectives, methodology, and the standardisation landscape per technology area. It identifies cross-cutting gaps and opportunities for BorderForce contributions, defines the standardisation roadmap, and includes risk assessment and governance mechanisms for standardisation activities.

Finally, Chapter 7 summarises the main conclusions and next steps, providing a clear foundation for the continued communication, dissemination, exploitation and standardisation efforts in the project’s upcoming period (M16–M30).

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1 INTRODUCTION

1.1 Purpose of the Document

The Deliverable D6.2 - “Initial Communication, Dissemination, Advisory Board Activities and Exploitation/Standardisation Plan” is defined under WP6 - “Initial Communication, Dissemination, Exploitation and Standardisation” of the BorderForce project (GA No 101168316).

The purpose of this deliverable is to report on the communication, dissemination and Advisory Board activities carried out during the first period of the project (M1-M15) and to outline the exploitation and standardisation plans, providing a clear overview of measures to maximise the impact and uptake of project results.

1.2 Document Scope

The BorderForce project aims to strengthen the efficiency and effectiveness of border surveillance systems for both single- and multi-agency operations at Europe’s external borders through the development, deployment and validation of a continuous 24/7 monitoring platform. By integrating diverse sensors and technologies into a unified intelligent detection system, the project delivers reliable and actionable support for operational and tactical decision-making.

The purpose of this deliverable D6.2 is to report on the communication, dissemination, and Advisory Board activities carried out throughout the project, building upon the *Initial Communication and Dissemination Plan* established in Month 3. It also outlines the exploitation and standardisation plans for the project results. The deliverable provides a structured overview of measures undertaken to maximise visibility, impact, and uptake of the outcomes, reflecting the progress made up to Month 15 and ensuring alignment with relevant market needs and standardisation frameworks.

1.3 Partners

This deliverable, D6.2, was coordinated and prepared by GSH, as the lead of both WP6 and this deliverable. Contributions to specific sections were provided by project partners: AIT provided the content on Advisory Board activities and ED developed the Standardisation plan.

1.4 Acronyms and abbreviations

Acronym / Abbreviation	Explanation
ADS-B	Automatic Dependent Surveillance – Broadcast
AI	Artificial Intelligence
AIS	Automatic Identification System
AR	Augmented Reality
C2	Command and Control
CEN	European Committee for Standardization (Comité Européen de Normalisation)
CENELEC	European Committee for Electrotechnical Standardization (Comité Européen de Normalisation Électrotechnique)
CIRAM	Common Integrated Risk Analysis Model

ConOps	Concept of Operations
CSDP	Common Security and Defence Policy
CWA	CEN Workshop Agreement
DoA	Description of the Action
Dx.y	Deliverable
EO	Earth Observation
ESA	European Space Agency
ETSI	European Telecommunications Standards Institute
EU	European Union
FCT	Fight Against Crime and Terrorism
GA	Grant Agreement
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
GIS	Geographic Information System
IEEE	Institute of Electrical and Electronics Engineers
IEC	International Electrotechnical Commission
INSPIRE	Infrastructure for Spatial Information in the European Community
IoT	Internet of Things
IPR	Intellectual Property Rights
ISO	International Organisation for Standardisation
ITU	International Telecommunication Union
KER	Key Exploitable Result
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
LAN	Local Area Network
MR	Mixed Reality
NATO	North Atlantic Treaty Organisation
NDA	Non-Disclosure Agreement
OGC	Open Geospatial Consortium
OSINT	Open Source Intelligence
Q&A	Questions and Answers
R&D	Research and Development
RF	Radio Frequency
RP1	Reporting Period 1
SAR	Synthetic Aperture Radar
SDO	Standards-Developing Organisations
SWOT	Strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities, Threats
TRL	Technology Readiness Level
UAS	Unmanned Aerial System
UAV	Unmanned Aerial Vehicle
UNESCO	United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organisation
WG	Working Group
WP	Work Package
XR	Extended Reality

1.5 References

- BorderForce Grant Agreement (GA) with No. 101168316)
- BorderForce Consortium Agreement (CA)
- Project Homepage: <https://BorderForce-horizon.eu/>
- BorderForce: Deliverable D6.1 - Initial Communication and Dissemination Plan V1.0 – 01/2025

2 DELIVERABLE DESCRIPTION

Deliverable D6.2 – “Initial Communication, Dissemination, Advisory Board Activities, and Exploitation/Standardisation Plan,” coordinated by GSH and prepared in collaboration with AIT (Advisory Board Activities) and ED (Standardisation Plan), has been produced under the framework of WP6 of the BorderForce project. Planned for submission in Month 15, this deliverable implements the work plan outlined in the GA and covers all four specific tasks of WP6.

This document consists of the following chapters:

- The Publishable Executive Summary of the deliverable.
- Chapter 1 which includes the Introduction, outlining the purpose, scope, partners involved and relevant acronyms, and abbreviations.
- Chapter 2 provides the description of the deliverable including the presentation of its structure.
- Chapter 3 describes the communication and dissemination activities actually carried out.
- Chapter 4 presents the activities performed for Advisory Board engagement and external stakeholders’ outreach.
- Chapter 5 outlines the Exploitation Plan.
- Chapter 6 outlines the Standardisation Plan.
- Chapter 7 provides the Conclusions.

3 ACTUAL COMMUNICATION AND DISSEMINATION ACTIVITIES

3.1 Overview

Communication and dissemination activities in BorderForce are implemented in line with the strategy defined in D6.1 and are coordinated under WP6/ T6.1. During the first 15 months of the project, the consortium prioritised the establishment of a coherent public presence and the creation of reliable channels for structured outreach. This period focused on: (i) ensuring consistent presentation of the project's scope and progress through owned channels (website, social media and communication assets), (ii) providing regular, evidence-based updates on technical development and integration milestones, and (iii) strengthening engagement with end-users and policy-relevant stakeholders to ensure that communication remains aligned with operational needs, ethical constraints and security considerations.

3.1.1 Project Objectives

BorderForce is a Horizon Europe project that aims to strengthen European border surveillance by developing a flexible, transportable and interoperable solution that enhances situational awareness in complex and evolving operational environments. The concept integrates a self-sufficient Command and Control (C2) station with multi-source sensing (e.g., ground sensors, UAVs and satellite resources), supported by AI-enabled analytics, OSINT processing, and advanced user interfaces for timely threat assessment and decision support, while incorporating ethical, legal and fundamental-rights requirements throughout development and validation.

The objectives of the communication and dissemination strategy, as originally defined in D6.1, remain consistent and valid at M15. They aim to identify, structure, and coordinate the activities required to maximise the project's influence and impact, while also promoting secondary exploitation routes for BorderForce results. To ensure the widest possible dissemination of project achievements and to strengthen impact and outreach across relevant stakeholder communities, the BorderForce communication and dissemination objectives are set as follows:

- Define a clear and distinctive brand identity for BorderForce, consistent online and offline, which represents cornerstone project values
- Ensure broad visibility of BorderForce work and disseminate its results towards the targeted stakeholder groups so as to effectively promote the BorderForce offering for large uptake
- Facilitate the exploitation of BorderForce outcomes for the partners and for the overall research communities by promoting the development of innovative solutions for effective socio-economic impact creation
- Ensure broad visibility and promotion of BorderForce, beyond the programme borders via a strategic and operational coordination of the specific security communities through dedicated efforts embracing all target stakeholders
- Support the sustainability of BorderForce beyond the project lifetime.

3.1.2 Project values

The project values and key messaging principles were established in D6.1. This deliverable confirms their continued applicability and documents mid-project (15-month) implementation progress against these guiding principles:

- Operational relevance and end-user-driven development: Communication reflects the project’s requirements-led approach, scenario-based validation, and iterative feedback cycles with end-users across development and testing activities.
- Interoperability and modularity: Key messages highlight the project’s modular architecture and emphasis on integration, scalability and compatibility with existing systems and operational practices.
- Ethics-by-design and fundamental-rights considerations: Communication content is curated to ensure responsible framing of capabilities, protection of sensitive operational information, and continued attention to legal, ethical and societal requirements.

3.1.3 Visual Identity analysis

BorderForce visual identity continues to be based on the project logo, the blue–yellow colour palette and clean, technology-forward layouts. During the project, the consortium refreshed the social media cover templates to better reflect project progress (integration testing, end-user engagement and upcoming trials), while maintaining consistent EU funding acknowledgement, partner attribution and approval procedures.

Figure 1. BorderForce visual identity

Figure 2. BorderForce updated social media covers

3.1.4 Target Audience and Stakeholders

One of the most critical factors for an effective and successful communication and dissemination strategy is the accurate identification and segmentation of target stakeholders and audiences. In the context of BorderForce, this task is particularly relevant, as the current geopolitical instability has direct implications for state security, economic stability, citizens' quality of life, and the core values of European societies, such as safety

and freedom of movement. In this sense, BorderForce addresses issues that ultimately concern society as a whole, even if the project’s outputs are primarily targeted at specialised operational and institutional users.

Based on this context, several clusters of target audiences and stakeholders were identified:

At a first level, citizens, policy makers, and media constitute a broad audience group. While not direct users of the BorderForce system, they are key recipients of carefully curated, non-sensitive information that helps raise awareness of the importance of effective border surveillance, lawful use of technology, and the societal benefits of enhanced external border security.

As BorderForce is a research and innovation project, a second audience cluster includes actors with a direct interest in research, technology and innovation, such as private companies, R&D organisations, academic institutions, and investors. For this group, BorderForce communication focuses on technological innovation, integration approaches, validation through trials, and the potential for future exploitation and market uptake.

The third cluster comprises institutional and operational stakeholders that are directly relevant to border management and security. This includes national government departments, EU Agencies, law enforcement and intelligence bodies, border authorities, and customs organisations at EU, Member State and neighboring-country level (e.g. FRONTEX, Europol, DG HOME – Directorate-General for Migration and Home Affairs, and the Joint Research Centre (DG JRC) of the European Commission). These stakeholders represent the primary end users and policy shapers for BorderForce outcomes.

A structured overview of the main BorderForce target groups and their respective value propositions is provided in Table below.

Table 1. Target Audiences, BorderForce Grant Agreement.

STAKEHOLDERS	BorderForce VALUE PROPOSITION
Member States / Ministries and relevant government departments	New framework for the risk management, enhanced border security by leveraging a combination of physical surveillance and digital monitoring, operational flexibility, advanced technology integration such as extended reality and artificial intelligence, interoperability with legacy and planned systems and repurposing potential to other domains
Technology / service providers, investors, scientific community	Research and development opportunities through the integration of advanced technologies, easy integration of new technical solutions from the use of open standards (where applicable), intellectual property and licensing opportunities, market expansion and diversification since the project results can be used in other domains apart from border surveillance. Credibility and reference ability of results through system trials
Citizens / travelers, public media	Enhanced security and safety through improved border surveillance and monitoring, economic stability due to the increased efficiency of the border surveillance operations, reassurance that surveillance operations are lawful and proportional, ensuring border surveillance solutions keep pace

	with rapidly evolving risks in an increasingly interconnected world. Open borders (because of enhanced external security) within the Schengen-area allow facilitated border crossings
Regulators and policymakers	Comprehensive analysis of the ethics risks from the use of surveillance technology & of digital tools and new technologies. Understanding of the technologies as a key enabler to meet best practices and assess that legal / regulatory landscapes remain fit-for-purpose.

D6.2 provides a M1–M15 project update on the implementation of WP6 communication and dissemination activities, outlining progress to date, key outputs, and lessons learned. It also defines the next steps and priorities for the second period of the project to further strengthen visibility and impact.

3.2 Communication Activities

Communication activities focus on raising awareness of the project, maintaining a coherent public identity, and providing accessible updates on progress, while respecting confidentiality, security and ethics constraints. The following subsections summarise the tools and outputs implemented to date and planned next actions.

As defined in the deliverable D6.1 – “Initial Communication and Dissemination Plan”, BorderForce continues to apply the established set of communication methods and channels to ensure coherent outreach and effective dissemination. In the following table, the main project communication methods are presented:

Table 2. Communication methods, BorderForce Grant Agreement.

Project website	All relevant activities are accompanied with short reports, announcements, photos, news, and links to downloads.	1 Frequently updated
Social media	Only strictly authorised discussions and exchanges with online communities (e.g., LinkedIn, X)	> 50
Brochure	Electronic and hard copies of the project brochure comprehending a general overview of the project, its challenges and expected impacts in different languages to reach large audiences in different countries, including those where the BorderForce demonstrators will be carried out.	8
Posters	A set of posters will be designed and printed to exhibit at partners’ premises and use at events where the project takes presence.	>4
Institutional Presentation	Project Presentation will be created at the beginning of the project, containing basic information about the project (activities, objectives, partnerships, events).	1
Trial videos	A set of videos will be orchestrated, describing the use cases demonstration, their scope and the BorderForce technologies tested and evaluated.	>=4
Info-Graphics	Production of infographics to show the results in a clear and simple way. It is foreseen that during the project implementation phase, 10 infographics presenting various outcomes will be produced.	10

Banner	An attractive large size banner and one stand-up presenting a general image of the project aiming to capture a first interest/attention.	1+1
Final Publishable Report	A Final Publishable Report will be developed to summarise the project's objectives, activities, and achievements. This report will be result-oriented, it will present the tangible results of the project, lessons learnt, and impacts achieved, in order to convince and guide other regions and countries to engage in similar actions.	1
Articles	Tailor-made articles and interviews for publications and other targeted media channels (e.g., EC newsletters, specialised national magazines etc.). Focus will be on AI, technology advancements, security practitioners' methods and demonstration results.	>=5
Newsletter	Periodic newsletters development, publication, and distribution to all the participating partners, conference attendees, website visitors, and other perceived stakeholders / interested parties.	>4, periodical
Press releases	Press releases will be issued to specialised and general media channels at key project milestones (kick-off, major achievements, etc.). A press /media kit will be developed containing detailed press releases, videos (e.g., of project demos), publishable images from the project, few short papers (devoted to some key theme/topic of the project).	>=2
Talks in workshops	Invited talks in workshops and international events of reference as to communicate the project experimentation platform and solutions.	On invite
Innovation Events	Events (as special sessions during the planned hackathons and the large-scale virtual exercise) in Europe with strong stakeholders' representation so that the BorderForce story is spread.	>=1
Marketing Events	Marketing Event, with guided presentation of selected results.	>=1

3.2.1 Digital and Print material

A range of communication assets has already been produced and used across BorderForce communication and dissemination activities, in both digital and print-ready formats, including brochures, posters, infographics, and roll-up banners. These materials have been disseminated either as printed items during events, meetings and presentations, or as digital content through the project's communication channels (social media, newsletter and website).

Brochures have been used to provide a concise and structured overview of the project, presenting its scope, approach, and key milestones. Infographics have supported the clear and accessible communication of selected project concepts and results in a visual format suitable for both specialist and non-specialist audiences. Posters and roll-up banners have been prepared in alignment with specific event objectives and target audiences (e.g., scientific conferences, industrial exhibitions, and workshops with border authorities), ensuring that messaging and visual emphasis match the context.

Figure 3. BorderForce Brochure

Digital versions of these assets were made available for download via the BorderForce website. Additional material will be created in the coming months according to the evolving needs of the project and planned communication actions; where relevant, selected assets will also be prepared in additional languages to enhance accessibility for local stakeholder communities.

3.2.2 Institutional Presentation

A presentation was maintained for consortium and end-user briefings, highlighting objectives, architecture at a high level, validation progress and next steps. Partners use the presentation as a baseline and adapt it for specific audiences, keeping core messaging aligned.

Figure 4. BorderForce presentation

3.2.3 Website structure

The BorderForce project website (borderforce-horizon.eu) functions as the project's primary public-facing platform for communication and dissemination, ensuring that external stakeholders (end-user organisations, policy and research communities, industry, and the wider public) have a single, reliable point of access to official project information,

updates, and results. The homepage presents the BorderForce concept and provides direct navigation to the project's main content pillars, including the project's innovation topics and operational services.

Figure 5. BorderForce website

A key strength of the website is its structured presentation of BorderForce innovations, which are highlighted as distinct capability areas. These include (indicatively) AI-based object detection, a mobile/deployable command and control (C2) station supporting integrated mission workflows, and solutions related to drone security, as well as additional enabling technologies showcased through dedicated pages.

In parallel, the website describes BorderForce services that support early threat assessment and situational awareness, including the use of Open-Source Intelligence (OSINT) to process online information relevant to border security contexts. This content helps communicate the project's operational relevance by linking technical components to practical service outcomes and user needs.

The website is also designed to directly support dissemination and reporting by offering content categories that can be referenced and reused in project communications (e.g., innovation/service pages and news posts). The **News** section is used to publish short articles on project activities and milestones (e.g., consortium meetings and events), providing information and an accessible record of progress for external audiences.

The **Partners** page presents the consortium and provides stakeholders with an overview of the organisations involved. This supports transparency and enables external audiences to identify expertise and potential collaboration points

The **Library** is the website's repository space for public project outputs. It is explicitly positioned to host public deliverables and other relevant consortium material, supporting open dissemination and long-term accessibility of results.

The website integrates **social media** links as recognizable platform icons (e.g., Facebook, X/Twitter, YouTube, LinkedIn, Instagram). These are displayed as part of the site's recurring layout (notably visible on content pages), supporting traffic to project social channels and reinforcing multi-channel dissemination.

The project website featured a dedicated newsletter subscription section, enabling visitors to sign up and receive project updates by email.

The Contact page and website footer provide a clear communication route to the project’s dissemination lead team (“Contact the BorderForce Communication Team”), including the official project email and organisational context, supporting stakeholder engagement, media inquiries, and collaboration requests. Across the site, the footer consistently includes the Horizon Europe funding acknowledgement and disclaimer text (with the Grant Agreement reference visible on all pages), copyright attribution, and a clearly presented contact block with the communication team details. In addition, the website explicitly states that BorderForce is funded by the EU Horizon Europe Research and Innovation Programme under Grant Agreement No. 101168316, reinforcing transparency and compliance with EU communication obligations.

3.2.4 Social Media

BorderForce maintains an active and frequently updated social media presence to communicate project progress, milestones, and engagement activities to relevant stakeholders. LinkedIn serves as the primary channel, while consortium partners actively amplify posts through their own networks to extend reach and visibility. In addition, the project maintains accounts on Facebook, Instagram and X (formerly Twitter) to broaden outreach and engage wider audiences. Midway through the project, the social media cover visuals were refreshed to better showcased project progress, while maintaining the established BorderForce visual identity. Social media activities are supported by a content calendar and the consistent use of key hashtags to strengthen discoverability and thematic positioning, including #borderforce #bordersurveillance #externalsecurity.

Figure 6. BorderForce Social media

A key communication activity is the LinkedIn series “The Floor to the Partners”, which presents consortium partners and showcases their role in the project through short, engaging posts. The series is planned to include 16 posts, with an average posting frequency of approximately one post every two months. Each post combines a brief partner introduction with their expectations, experiences, and lessons learned, following a logical order aligned with work package timelines to ensure a steady flow of relevant content throughout the project.

Implementation of the series has already started: the first post featured VTT (User Requirements), and the second post highlighted Securiton GmbH, focusing on the industrial tests and the project’s progress in industrial validation. Partner input for “The Floor to the Partners” is expected to increase in the coming months, supported by technical studies, validation activities, and other concrete results that will provide richer material for upcoming posts.

Figure 7. BorderForce LinkedIn “The floor to the partners”

Figure 8. BorderForce LinkedIn “The floor to the partners”

3.2.5 Videos

Short videos (where permitted) were used to support storytelling around system demonstrations, integration milestones, and trial preparation. All audiovisual material is

produced and shared following the project’s internal approval workflow, ensuring compliance with confidentiality requirements and operational constraints. The approved videos are uploaded to the BorderForce website and shared through the project’s communication channels.

Study visit to Lithuania January 2025

The video showcases the BorderForce team’s visit to the State Border Guard Service of Lithuania, carried out as part of the project’s research activities. It highlights the operational context and objectives of BorderForce: developing advanced technological capabilities to support the protection of the EU’s external land borders, contribute to the management of irregular migration, and provide tools to counter smuggling from third countries.

Videos

Figure 9. BorderForce video

Study visit to Bulgaria April 2025

The video features highlights from the BorderForce technical study visit in Bulgaria (April 2025), including on-site meetings and technical discussions with end users, exchanges on operational needs and real-world challenges, and scenes with GLAVNA DIREKTSIA GRANICHNA POLITSIA and the BULGARIAN DEFENCE INSTITUTE.

Industrial tests Securiton November 2025

In November 2025, the BorderForce consortium completed a full week of industrial system tests at Securiton GmbH (Germany), focusing on integrating and validating key components under realistic operational workflows, with active end-user participation and feedback. A short video capturing the test activities, demonstrations, and debriefing outcomes is currently in production and will be published on the project website and social media in the coming weeks.

3.2.6 Articles

Articles and news items are published through the project website and partner communication channels to highlight key milestones, meetings, and non-sensitive results.

In this context, an article titled “BorderForce - A Flexible System Extending Automated Border Surveillance funded by the EU Horizon Programme” was published in the March/April issue of Border Security Report.

Publications

Figure 10. BorderForce Article

3.2.7 Newsletter

The BorderForce newsletter is a key communication channel designed to keep stakeholders informed about project progress, milestones, results, and upcoming activities. It provides a concise overview of technical developments, validation work, events, and dissemination actions, while ensuring that all communications and contact management follow GDPR requirements. The newsletter is planned to be produced approximately every six months, with contributions from all partners (e.g., short texts, photos, case studies, and key achievements), and supported by dissemination through partners' own networks.

In this context, the first BorderForce digital newsletter was sent at the end of October 2025 (30/10/2025) to project partners via the mailing list all-borderforce@list.ait.ac.at (currently 83 contacts) and to individuals who subscribed through the project website, and partners were encouraged to further disseminate it to their target audiences through their own channels. The newsletter was issued using the Brevo email marketing tool, and a direct registration link is available on the project website to enable GDPR-compliant subscriptions. The same newsletter was also uploaded to the BorderForce website under Media → Digital Material to ensure easy access for a wider audience. Because there was limited content available during the project's first months, only one newsletter was released during this reporting period, instead of the two foreseen according to the plan.

1st Newsletter autumn 2025

Welcome to the BorderForce newsletter! In this edition, we will introduce the project's scope, objectives, and highlight its initial progress. BorderForce is an EU-funded project under the Horizon Europe programme. It officially started in November 2024 and will run until April 2027, bringing together leading partners from across Europe to develop innovative solutions for safer, smarter, and more resilient border management.

Subscribe to our newsletter

Set the working axes:

Kick-off meeting in Vienna

In November 2024 in Vienna, the BorderForce project was launched with a successful Kick-off Meeting, where all partners came together to establish a shared vision and align on the project's objectives, scope and initial action plan.

This meeting laid the groundwork for effective collaboration and set the path for the upcoming activities aimed at enhancing cross-border security and cooperation based on the following approach.

Figure 11. BorderForce Newsletter

Figure 12. BorderForce website - Newsletter

Subscribe to our newsletter

Email Address *

Subscribe

Figure 13. BorderForce website – Subscribe to Newsletter section

3.2.8 Press Release

Press releases and press-style announcements are used in BorderForce as a targeted communication instrument to inform a wider audience about key project milestones, events, and non-sensitive achievements, while ensuring consistency with security, confidentiality, and ethical requirements. These communications focus on high-level messages that present the project's objectives, relevance, and progress in an accessible manner, without disclosing sensitive technical or operational details.

During the reporting period, press release-type content has been published and consolidated through the official BorderForce website, in particular via the Media -> News page. This section functions as repository for public-facing announcements and already includes coverage of important meetings, technical studies, study visits, and consortium meetings, alongside other communication-relevant activities. The published news items support transparency, provide a traceable public record of project progress, and serve as reusable material for amplification through partner websites, newsletters, and social media channels. At the same time, the website News section is not the only outlet for press-style communications, as key announcements are also disseminated through partner channels, including partner websites, newsletters, and social media, to reach wider and more targeted audiences.

Press releases and news items are coordinated under WP6, with contributions from consortium partners, and follow internal review and approval procedures prior to publication. In the second period, the News section will continue to be used to communicate validated outcomes, major demonstrations, and policy-relevant milestones, supporting sustained visibility and impact of BorderForce beyond the immediate project community.

3.2.9 Final Publishable Report

The Final Publishable Report is foreseen for the second period of the project and is expected to serve as a clear reference document for external stakeholders, including other projects and countries seeking to engage in initiatives similar to BorderForce.

The work carried out during the first period will contribute to this report, including a communication-focused summary of the project's objectives, activities, and achievements, in line with the overall communication plan.

3.2.10 Events

Events are leveraged in BorderForce both for communication (increasing visibility) and dissemination (supporting knowledge transfer). Communication-oriented participation typically includes presentations, booth /exhibition material, and project overview sessions addressed to mixed stakeholder audiences, while dissemination activities focus on targeted exchanges around validated, non-sensitive project outputs.

During the reporting period, BorderForce was represented at key events, including RSCY2025 (Cyprus) and Beyond Expo 2025 (Greece) as exhibitor. In addition, GSH and AIT represented the project at the "Projects to Policy" Seminar in Brussels (4–5 June 2025), contributing to dialogue on how project results can inform policy discussions. BorderForce

also participated in the Greek Space Tech Forum 2025 as an exhibitor and sponsor, further strengthening outreach to the national and European innovation ecosystem.

Moreover, BorderForce participated in Space Tech Expo Europe 2025 (Bremen, Germany, 18–20 November 2025), enhancing visibility within the European space and innovation community and enabling exchanges with stakeholders relevant to space-enabled services for situational awareness and border surveillance.

3.2.11 Podcasts

BorderForce will introduce short, podcast-style audio as an additional communication medium to share project insights in a clear and accessible way, while carefully managing the risk of misinterpretation or misuse. This activity will be oriented primarily to end-users (rather than the wider public) and will focus on high-level, end-user relevant topics such as the project's rationale, expected operational value, key strengths and potential, interoperability considerations, and the overall testing and validation approach; without disclosing sensitive or confidential technical or operational details.

AIT has already completed the necessary technical production tests successfully. To further reduce exposure and ensure controlled dissemination, episodes will not be released via open platforms (e.g., Spotify); instead, they will be made available as audio files hosted on the project website and promoted through partner channels to reach targeted end-user audiences. The first episode is planned for January - February 2026. Episodes will follow a structured “prepared conversation” (guided Q&A) format, with a target duration of up to 15 minutes, and topics will be defined progressively with partner input in line with project progress and communication opportunities.

3.3 Dissemination Activities

International engagement with industry innovators and technology stakeholders continues to be a central pillar of BorderForce dissemination. By M15, consortium partners actively leverage their sector networks to promote the project's value proposition and to share validated, non-sensitive insights on system development, integration progress, and emerging capabilities. This outreach strengthens visibility among solution providers and market actors, while also supporting pathways for future uptake and exploitation of BorderForce outcomes.

In parallel, BorderForce communication targets institutional and decision-making audiences, including ministries and competent government departments, European agencies and operational networks, and leadership in research and academia. For these stakeholders, the consortium provides structured, policy and operations relevant information highlighting BorderForce contributions to border-management priorities, interoperability, and responsible technology deployment.

While established partner networks remain an effective entry point for dissemination, BorderForce maintains an outward-looking approach. The consortium continues to expand its stakeholder map and pursue new collaborations and synergies with complementary initiatives and communities, with the aim to avoid duplication, reinforce coherence across EU efforts, and strengthen long-term impact potential.

3.3.1 Participation in Events

Participation in events and external engagements was a core element of BorderForce dissemination during the first reporting period, with a clear emphasis on activities that strengthen operational relevance, support validation, and build visibility within practitioner, policy, and innovation communities; in addition, BorderForce was actively represented in industry, innovation, and policy-facing engagements to increase visibility, build stakeholder connections, and position project results within relevant ecosystems:

- RSCY2025 (Cyprus, 17-19 March 2025): BorderForce participated as a sponsor, supporting outreach to the regional and international research, security, and innovation community.
- Beyond Expo 2025 (Greece, 4-6 April 2025): BorderForce participated as an exhibitor, engaging with technology providers, industry stakeholders, and the broader innovation ecosystem.
- “Projects to Policy” Seminar (Brussels, 4-5 June 2025): GSH and AIT represented BorderForce, contributing to discussions on how research outcomes and validated project results can inform policy considerations and future capability planning.
- Greek Space Tech Forum 2025 (Greece, 1-2 July 2025): BorderForce participated as an exhibitor and sponsor, further strengthening outreach within the national and European innovation ecosystem and supporting connections relevant to space-enabled services and situational awareness.
- Space Tech Expo Europe 2025 (Bremen, Germany, 18-20 November 2025): BorderForce participated to strengthen outreach to the space and innovation ecosystem and engage with stakeholders relevant to space-enabled border surveillance, including Earth observation, satellite communications and geospatial.

During the first period, BorderForce actively used internal project events, particularly technical study visits and industrial testing activities (State Border Guard Service technical visit, Glavna Direktsia Granichna Politsia and Bulgarian Defence Institute technical visit, SecuriDrone Test Center industrial tests (Securiton GmbH), as a source of dissemination content. Non-sensitive insights and outcomes from these engagements (e.g., validated operational needs, scenario refinement, integration progress, and key lessons learned) were distilled into high-level messages and communication assets to support coordinated outreach through project social media, project website and partner channels, while fully respecting security, confidentiality, and ethical requirements.

3.3.2 Articles to specialised press

As part of the targeted dissemination activities towards professional and sector-specific audiences, an article entitled “BorderForce - A Flexible System Extending Automated Border Surveillance funded by the EU Horizon Programme” was published in the March/April 2025 issue of the [Border Security Report](#).

The article presents the BorderForce project to a specialised readership, highlighting its objectives, innovative approach, and relevance for modern border surveillance and security operations. By focusing on the project’s flexible and interoperable system concept, as well as its alignment with EU priorities and Horizon Europe funding, the publication contributes to raising awareness among border-security professionals, industry stakeholders, and decision-makers. This dissemination action supports the positioning of BorderForce within

the international border-security community and strengthens the visibility of project results beyond academic and project internal channels.

3.3.3 Targeted meetings with policy makers

Targeted engagement with policy makers and regulatory stakeholders is an integral element of the BorderForce communication and dissemination approach, and all consortium partners are expected to contribute according to their role, networks and national context. Liaison with policy makers, regulators, national government bodies and relevant European agencies serves a dual purpose: (i) to increase awareness of BorderForce objectives, progress and validated results, and (ii) to support informed dialogue on policy-relevant aspects of the project, including interoperability needs, operational deployment considerations, and ethics-by-design and fundamental rights safeguards.

To maximise effectiveness, partners coordinate the preparation of tailored briefings and, where appropriate, joint delegation teams to deliver coherent and compelling presentations to key third parties and institutional stakeholders (e.g., FRONTEX, Europol, and DG HOME). These targeted meetings support alignment with EU border management priorities and facilitate early visibility of findings that may inform future operational practices, capability planning, or policy discussions.

Implementation of these activities builds on the stakeholder analysis and questionnaire-based feedback collected and analyzed in D6.1. The questionnaire results provided evidence on stakeholder priorities, information needs, and preferred communication channels, confirming the importance of operational relevance, interoperability, and validated results for key audiences. These insights have informed the refinement of target-group segmentation, the emphasis on operational and validation-driven messaging, and the selection of dissemination formats and channels applied during the reporting period.

Engagement is scheduled in connection with key project milestones, such as periodic reviews and major demonstrations, and is implemented through curated presentations, concise briefing notes, and structured feedback collection. The feedback gathered through these exchanges is used to refine messaging, identify policy-related requirements or constraints, and support the exploitation and uptake pathways of BorderForce results within relevant EU and national security communities.

3.4 Monitoring Communication and Dissemination

3.4.1 Evaluation, Monitoring Communication activities

To ensure the effectiveness of BorderForce communication and dissemination activities and to enable timely corrective actions when needed, all relevant efforts are continuously monitored and evaluated throughout the project lifespan. The monitoring framework is anchored in the Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) defined in the Dissemination and Communication Plan, which provide a common baseline for both quantitative tracking (e.g., number of outputs, website/social media performance, stakeholder engagement) and qualitative assessment (e.g., relevance, clarity, consistency with project messaging and constraints).

KPI performance is reviewed at regular intervals and at key reporting milestones to assess progress against targets, identify trends, and document any improvement measures.

Where monitoring outcomes indicate that adjustments are required due to evolving project priorities, stakeholder needs, or the maturity of project results, the KPI set and targets may be refined in subsequent updates to ensure that evaluation remains fit for purpose and supports continuous improvement of BorderForce communication and dissemination activities.

3.4.2 Objectives

Monitoring of Communication and Dissemination in BorderForce aims to ensure that outreach activities remain strategic, coherent and effective throughout the project. The monitoring framework supports (i) verifying that communication actions reach the intended stakeholder groups and convey the agreed key messages, (ii) tracking progress against the objectives and indicators defined in the Dissemination and Communication Plan, and (iii) ensuring compliance with Horizon Europe visibility requirements as well as project specific constraints related to confidentiality, security, ethics and fundamental rights. In addition, monitoring enables timely identification of gaps or underperforming channels and provides the basis for evidence-based adjustments, thereby supporting continuous improvement and maximising overall impact.

3.4.3 Monitoring

Communication and Dissemination monitoring is coordinated by WP6 and implemented with contributions from all partners through systematic tracking of activities and outputs. Monitoring combines quantitative tracking (e.g., communication outputs produced and distributed, participation in events, stakeholder engagement actions, social media activity and newsletter distribution) with qualitative observation (e.g., relevance of audiences reached, quality of interactions, stakeholder feedback and lessons learned). Partners record and report their dissemination actions on a regular basis, allowing consolidation at project level and ensuring consistency for periodic reporting.

In parallel, the project monitors content published through official channels website, social media, newsletters and specialized press, to ensure that information is accurate, aligned with the project narrative, and approved according to internal procedures. Particular attention is given to adherence to confidentiality and IPR provisions, and to ensure that public communication remains appropriate and non-sensitive, especially when referring to operational scenarios, end-user involvement, or system capabilities.

Table 3. BorderForce Communication methods and relevant KPIs, BorderForce Grant Agreement.

Communication method	KPIs
Project web site	1 Frequently updated
Social media	> 50
Brochure	8
Posters	>4
Institutional Presentation	1
Trial videos	>=4

InfoGraphics	10
Banner	1+1
Final Publishable Report	1
Articles	>=5
Newsletter	>4 periodical
Press releases	>=2
Talks in workshops	on invite
Innovation Events	>=1
Marketing Events	>=1

Table 4. BorderForce Communication methods and relevant KPIs, BorderForce Grant Agreement.

Type	KPIs
Exhibition stands in the industry innovation events/fairs	>5
Publication in highly ranked international journals and magazines	>8
Contributions in international peer-reviewed conferences	>8
Cluster with European projects and other initiatives	>5
Targeted Meetings with policy makers	>6

3.4.4 Evaluation

Evaluation builds on the monitoring results by assessing the effectiveness and contribution to impact of the implemented Communication and Dissemination activities. It examines performance against the objectives and KPIs defined in the Dissemination and Communication Plan, using both quantitative evidence (reach, engagement, outputs, participation) and qualitative evidence (stakeholder responses, usefulness of materials, uptake signals, and relevance to policy/practitioner communities). Evaluation outcomes are reviewed at key reporting milestones to identify what works well and where improvements are needed.

Where the evaluation indicates that changes are required due to project maturity, availability of results, stakeholder interest, or external context, WP6 proposes targeted corrective actions. These may include refining messages, adjusting channel mix, strengthening engagement with specific stakeholder groups, or prioritising dissemination formats better suited to validated results. This iterative process ensures that BorderForce Communication and Dissemination remains fit-for-purpose, measurable, and impact-oriented across the project duration. During this reporting period, one project brochure was produced, compared to the eight brochures foreseen for the full project duration. The brochure template can be adapted in different formats and sizes (e.g., print-ready and digital versions) and translated into additional languages to support wider dissemination across target audiences.

Table 5. BorderForce Communication methods and relevant KPIs, BorderForce Grant Agreement & achieved.

Communication method	KPIs	Achieved M1-M15
Project web site	Frequently updated	Frequently updated
Social media posts	> 50	64
Brochure	8	1 + different languages
Posters	>4	1
Institutional Presentation	1	1
Trial videos	>=4	0
InfoGraphics	10	3
Banner	1+1	1+1
Final Publishable Report	1	0
Articles	>=5	1
Newsletter	>4 periodical	1
Press releases	>=2	5
Talks in workshops	on invite	0
Innovation Events	>=1	3
Marketing Events	>=1	2

Table 6. BorderForce Communication methods and relevant KPIs, BorderForce Grant Agreement & achieved.

Type	KPIs	Achieved M1-M15
Exhibition stands in the industry innovation events/fairs	>5	3
Publication in highly ranked international journals and magazines	>8	1
Contributions in international peer-reviewed conferences	>8	2
Cluster with European projects and other initiatives	>5	2
Targeted Meetings with policy makers	>6	1

3.5 Discussion and Next Steps

This deliverable provides the updated mid-project (M1-M15) overview of BorderForce communication and dissemination implementation, building on the strategy and governance framework established in D6.1. It consolidates the objectives, key messages, target stakeholder groups, channels, and monitoring approach applied during the first 15 months, and serves as a reference point for the coordinated continuation of WP6 activities in the remaining project period.

At the same time, the deliverable documents achieved communication outputs and the mechanisms put in place to ensure consistent project visibility through the official website, social media presence, newsletters, and reusable communication assets, while maintaining alignment with ethical, legal, and security constraints. It also outlines the intended direction for the second half of the project, where dissemination will increasingly emphasize validated results, lessons learned from integration and trials, and exploitation-relevant outcomes, with content adapted to stakeholder needs and event contexts.

Finally, the Dissemination and Communication Plan and its KPI-based monitoring approach provide BorderForce with a robust framework to track performance, identify gaps, and introduce corrective actions where necessary. This ensures that communication and dissemination efforts remain targeted, credible, and impact oriented, supporting both the uptake of BorderForce results by relevant communities and the long-term visibility and sustainability of the project beyond its lifetime.

4 ADVISORY BOARD AND EXTERNAL STAKEHOLDERS OUTREACH - ACTIVITIES PERFORMED

A dynamic external stakeholders outreach is a key for enhancing the visibility and the interest around the BorderForce solution. Given though that the project was still in its early development phase until January 2026, most of the activities undertaken during this first period were meant to set the basis for further and deeper exchanges within the community in the future.

4.1 Advisory Board

First and foremost, the BorderForce Consortium has set up an Advisory Board as stated in the DoA to get guidance and feedback on its work. Several members from different countries and disciplines have been chosen in order to get complementary views on all the areas covered by the project:

- Mr. Pertti Woitsch, CEO from Woitsch Consulting, specialized in international sales, marketing and business development.
- Lieutenant Colonel Heikki Ojala, Deputy Director at the Border and Coast Guard Academy of the Finnish Border Guard
- Mr. Maurizio Gazzola, Head of Technology - Senior Information Systems Officer at the United Nations Office of Counter Terrorism
- Mr. Paolo Salieri, former Principal Scientific Officer at the EU, DG Migration and Home affairs
- Mr. Paolo Venturoni, Chief Executive Officer at European Organisation for Security
- Mr. Philipp Agathonos, Ambassador of Austrian in Vietnam; Common Security and Defence Policy (CSDP) trainee.
- Mrs. Isabela Rosal Santos, legal researcher at CiTiP (KU Leuven) specialized in cybersecurity, trustworthy data sharing, and data protection projects

Those experts entered the Advisory Board after having duly signed an NDA.

Four of them have joined the first Advisory Board meeting on November 12th 2024 (held within the BorderForce Kickoff Event in Vienna). A first fruitful exchange has taken place between the Consortium and the external experts concerning the main objectives of the project and the preferred approaches to reach them.

Since then, some experts have been contacted on an individual basis for specific topics, like Mr. Philip Agathonos on the CSDP for the requirements* or Mrs. Isabela Rosal Santos to discuss the Deliverable 2.4 (public).

The next Advisory Board meeting is set for March 16th 2026 in Greece, where the Consortium will present its progresses and first achievements. Some experts have already confirmed their participation.

4.2 Border Authorities & official bodies

The BorderForce Consortium consists of diverse partners already active in the border management community.

Since the beginning of the project, the Coordinator has been maintaining a regular contact with Frontex, who was represented at the BorderForce Kickoff Meeting by Mr. Dragos Voicu. Further discussion has been ongoing concerning the Common Information, Risk Analysis and Management (CIRAM) framework. The BorderForce website should also be soon linked onto the Frontex Website.

Other regular exchanges are happening between the Consortium and the EU, mainly via meetings proposed by the Community for European Research and Innovation for Security (CERIS) or the DG HOME. In that sense, the Consortium has participated to the Project to Policy seminar organized by the first one in June 2025 and the Coordinator has represented the project in a meeting set by the FCT section of the latter in December 2025.

A special BorderForce Presentation has been drafted to be shared with relevant authorities linked to the project.

4.3 *Initiate synergies with similar EU projects*

BorderForce actively seeks synergies with related EU-funded projects and thematic clusters to exchange best practices on interoperability, data sharing, ethics-by-design, and operational validation. These collaborations enhance efficiency and impact by avoiding duplication, identifying complementarities, and enabling coordinated dissemination activities such as joint workshops and clustered event sessions.

In this context, BorderForce remains proactive in establishing cooperation with projects sharing common objectives or technological foundations. Some relevant projects have already been identified and initial contacts have been established; these collaborations will be further strengthened in the next phases of the project and additional relevant initiatives may be included as the project progresses. Additional details are provided in Section 4.3 of this deliverable.

Possible contacts include, indicatively:

- [SEAGUARD](#) (ends 2027)

SEAGUARD aims to enhance maritime border surveillance and situational awareness by combining sensor technologies, data fusion, and intelligent analytics, supporting authorities in detecting and responding to maritime security risks.

- [Starlight](#) (ends 2026)

Starlight focuses on enhancing the EU's strategic autonomy in the field of artificial intelligence for law enforcement agencies (LEAs), developing trustworthy AI-based tools that support operational decision-making while respecting ethical and legal requirements.

- [THEIA project](#) (ends 2027)

THEIA is an EU-funded Horizon Europe project that enhances Copernicus Security services for crisis management by applying geospatial AI (GeoAI) and machine learning to fuse, process and analyse EO data—supporting faster, better-informed responses to challenges such as forced population displacement and climate-driven emergencies. Partners and the project coordinator of THEIA also participate in BorderForce, which facilitates the establishment and further development of collaboration between the two projects.

- [PopEye project](#)

PopEye (robust Privacy-Preserving Biometric Technologies for Passenger Identification and Verification at EU External Borders) is a Horizon Europe research project for improved identity verification, enhanced security, and a better border crossing experience. They optimise the efficiency and operational capabilities of border guards through novel on-the-move biometric solutions and offer travellers a smoother journey.

In addition, cooperation contacts have been established with the EURMARS project (completed in September 2025), given that several EURMARS partners also participate in BorderForce. The [EURMARS](#) project aims to develop an advanced platform to improve European Multi-Authority Border Security efficiency and cooperation. It focuses on interoperability, information sharing, and coordinated decision-making across multiple authorities involved in border management and surveillance.

A short collaboration with the EU project [MultiRATE](#) (Holistic framework for the MatUrity evaluation of ReAdiness level for security TEchnologies) has been performed in spring 2025: Partners AIT, ED, GSH, ECOE, SECU and HSE have provided the BorderForce TRL assessment results based on the MultiRATE framework.

The Consortium has also been in contact with the [Detection Hub](#), a collaborative dissemination and communication initiative led by the Center of Security Studies (KEMEA). It gathers multiple EU funded projects to discuss how scientific and innovative approaches can respond to the challenges faced by LEAs and also engage a large range of stakeholders to ensure strong synergies within the community. The Detection Hub enables each EU project to present its progresses and findings (up to the point of their development), identify common targets and exploitation capabilities and inform the market and potential end-users from various sectors (Police and Custom Authorities, prisons, Agencies etc.). The Consortium plans to present its achievements during the second phase of the project.

4.4 Other

Partner SECU has received an offer from one of its suppliers to promote BorderForce by publishing a statement concerning their support in an EU funded R&D project.

4.5 Next Steps

In the second phase of the project, the BorderForce Consortium plans to strengthen its links to the border management community, starting with participation in international events.

Unfortunately, the Security Research Event hosted by Frontex every two years is not planned to happen during the course of the project; nevertheless, partners plan to take part in the following events:

- World Border Congress, 14-16 April 2026, Vienna, Austria
- The Research and Innovation Symposium for European Security and Defense (RISE-SD), 15-16 April 2026, Varna, Bulgaria
- European Association for Biometrics – Research Projects Conference, 16-17 September 2026, Darmstadt, Germany

Such major conferences enable to present the project on a large scale and discuss its outcomes with the Community.

If the Consortium will naturally check whether further events will be proposed by Frontex, DG Home or CERIS in the course of 2026 / beginning of 2027, it will also invite these stakeholders to take part in the field trials planned during the second phase of the project. Partners consider this an ideal opportunity for relevant authorities to get first-hand impressions on the BorderForce solution and start to spread the word about the findings of the project.

Further than this, BorderForce plans to focus more efforts on the cooperation with the other EU projects listed in the section 4.3 to contribute to a strengthened, interoperable Border Management community.

5 OUTLINE OF EXPLOITATION PLAN

5.1 Overview

This deliverable documents the initial exploitation strategy of BorderForce for the period M1–M15. It provides a structured baseline for exploitation work by (i) identifying and contextualising the Key Exploitable Results (KERs), (ii) describing the initial stakeholder and end-user landscape relevant to BorderForce, (iii) outlining a preliminary SWOT and competitor/market landscape relevant to the project’s innovation logic, (iv) setting out an initial route-to-market rationale and distribution channels, and (v) consolidating the individual exploitation intentions received from partners to date.

The content is intentionally proportionate to the maturity of the action at Month 15. A more detailed exploitation plan, including refined positioning and later-stage business/procurement readiness elements, will be further developed as the project progresses towards integration and operational validation. The project’s Description of the Action explicitly foresees progressive validation in operational environments and two field trials (Lithuania and Bulgaria) as the basis for lessons learned and increased maturity towards TRL 7, which will in turn enable more concrete exploitation commitments in the second project phase.

5.2 Exploitation approach and procedure (M1-M15)

In M1–M15, BorderForce exploitation work follows the process described in Task T6.4: continuous engagement with stakeholders and the consortium community, systematic identification and refinement of exploitable assets, and collection of individual partner exploitation intentions aligned with consortium IPR arrangements.

Two parallel streams underpin this initial exploitation approach. First, the consortium consolidates the exploitable asset list and clarifies preliminary exploitation pathways, with attention to system integration logic and the operational context described in the DoA (deployable C2 station, sensing and UAV features, OSINT-based threat assessment, novel interfaces and training, and multi-authority collaboration).

Second, the consortium applies a structured template for individual exploitation inputs so that partners with different roles (industrial technology providers, research organisations, public authorities/end users) can contribute consistent information that becomes comparable and usable in later exploitation planning.

This initial exploitation work is also framed by Horizon Europe exploitation obligations under the GA: beneficiaries must use best efforts to exploit results up to four years after the end of the action, and results ownership-protection-licensing decisions must be managed accordingly (including joint ownership arrangements and access rights).

5.3 Key Exploitable Results (KERs) at Month 15

BorderForce addresses evolving border-security needs by enhancing real-time surveillance and situational awareness through a flexible, transportable command-and-control concept with configurable capabilities, integrating multiple sensing and monitoring technologies, including UAV-related functions, satellite resources, and open-source intelligence processing. The project also emphasises collaborative assessment, data exchange, new

user interfaces (including immersive technologies), and training approaches, while safeguarding fundamental rights and addressing ethical, legal and social aspects.

In this context, the consortium has consolidated the following KERs at Month 15. The list is expected to evolve and be refined as results mature and are validated.

KER-01 - Mobile/deployable C2 station equipped with advanced sensing for detecting persons, vehicles and UAVs, generating geo-referenced threat indicators (SECU).

This result is central to the project's concept of enabling rapid deployment of surveillance capability where fixed infrastructure is insufficient or where threat dynamics require temporary surge capacity. Its exploitation relevance is driven by operational demand for adaptable command-and-control solutions able to integrate multiple sensing streams and present geo-referenced indicators supporting decision-making. A realistic exploitation pathway at this stage is integration into solution offerings targeted at authorities and, where appropriate, operators of critical infrastructure, supported by controlled demonstrations, practitioner engagement and later procurement-oriented adoption based on validation evidence. Sensitivity and security considerations are expected to influence what elements can be broadly disseminated versus shared through controlled channels.

KER-02 - Autonomous mesh wireless communication network (ECoE).

This result supports resilient connectivity among deployable assets and distributed sensors, especially in environments with limited infrastructure. Exploitation relevance lies in enabling continuity of operations and secure data exchange under operational constraints. At Month 15, the most credible exploitation route is as an enabling module integrated into the overall system, strengthening the deployable concept and multi-asset coordination; standalone market positioning is considered premature until validated performance evidence is available.

KER-03 - OSINT platform tailored for generating regionally specific threat indicators (HSE, AIT).

This result addresses early threat assessment through the processing of online information sources to generate threat indicators relevant to border regions. Exploitation relevance is high for authorities seeking earlier warning and improved situational awareness, particularly where traditional sensors provide limited predictive insight. The initial exploitation route is operational uptake as an analytics capability feeding geo-referenced indicators and supporting collaborative assessment, with governance and compliance requirements (including data protection and ethical safeguards) considered integral to exploitability.

KER-04 - Novel visualisations for improved situation awareness and interactive training (VTT, AIT, ED).

This result supports improved comprehension and usability of complex information, including immersive or interactive approaches that enable training and collaborative assessment. Exploitation relevance is twofold: operational value (better situational awareness interfaces) and capability development (training tools that help practitioners interpret and act on indicators). The initial exploitation route is integration into the system prototype and adoption through practitioner training cycles, demonstrations and later

inclusion in procurement specifications; for software elements, licensing or reuse in subsequent deployments may be considered depending on consortium arrangements.

KER-05 - Understandable geo-referenced risk indicators and their fusion (HSE).

This result concerns the transformation of multi-source observations into interpretable geo-referenced risk indicators and their fusion, enabling consistent operational interpretation. Exploitation relevance lies in reducing cognitive load, supporting decision-making and enabling shared operational pictures across actors. The exploitation pathway depends strongly on validation evidence and on alignment with governance safeguards, particularly where indicators influence operational actions.

KER-06 - Specifications for cost-effective, energy-efficient deployable systems (All partners).

This result is primarily procurement-relevant knowledge intended to guide future deployments toward cost-effectiveness and energy efficiency. Its exploitation route is expected to be uptake by authorities and other stakeholders through specification development and procurement planning rather than commercialisation. This type of result supports sustainability of the project outcomes beyond technical components by enabling replication through documentation and procurement language.

KER-07 - Recommendations for environmentally sustainable and futureproof border surveillance systems (All partners).

This result provides guidance and recommendations supporting sustainability and futureproofing. Exploitation is expected through dissemination to relevant practitioner and policy communities and through integration into procurement and planning, helping authorities align technology choices with environmental and lifecycle considerations.

KER-08 - Interoperable and scalable BorderForce system architecture (ED).

This result provides an interoperability- and scalability-oriented architecture that enables integration of components and potential interaction with existing systems. Exploitation relevance is driven by the need for reusable integration patterns and scalable deployment across different operational contexts. The initial exploitation route is use as a reference architecture and integration blueprint, supporting replication and procurement readiness.

KER-09 - Identified privacy, ethical and social impacts and their mitigation and management measures (ETICAS).

This result strengthens deployability by addressing rights, ethics and social impacts as core design constraints. Exploitation relevance is high because it supports adoption by reducing legal/ethical risk, increasing trust, and providing deployable governance measures. The exploitation route is adoption as a practical “deployment-readiness” package (guidance, mitigation measures, monitoring processes) to accompany technical deployments and procurement requirements.

KER-10 - Operationalisation of cybersecurity and space standards into system design (All partners / ED).

This result supports secure deployment by translating relevant cybersecurity and space-related standards into the system's design principles and implementation choices. Exploitation is expected through reuse of security baselines and standards-aligned design approaches in deployments, procurement requirements and subsequent projects.

KER-11 - Compatibility and interoperability design for multi-authority missions (ED).

This result focuses on multi-authority interoperability and compatibility needs, supporting cross-organisation collaboration and mission-driven deployments. Exploitation is expected in mission planning, procurement specifications and governance arrangements, enabling authorities to adopt a more harmonised approach to joint operations.

KER-12 - BorderForce ConOps and requirements aligned with EU priorities through a capability-driven approach (VTT).

This result translates technical capabilities into an operational concept and requirement set. Exploitation relevance is high because concepts of operations and requirements are directly usable by authorities and integrators for planning, tender preparation, and alignment with strategic priorities. The exploitation route is mainly procurement-oriented uptake and reuse in future initiatives.

KER-13 - Verified BorderForce concept as blueprint for future border authority tenders (MOI).

This result reflects the project's ambition to provide a validated blueprint that can support future tendering and adoption. Exploitation is expected through procurement-oriented reuse and replication, particularly if validation activities provide credible evidence and clear implementation guidance.

KER-14 - AI-based object detection in satellite images (GSH).

This result delivers an end-to-end capability to acquire optical and SAR satellite imagery from online platforms, perform image pre-processing and run Machine Learning object detection (e.g., YOLOv7 / YOLOv9-E) to automatically detect objects of interest. It produces georeferenced bounding boxes with confidence scores, enabling rapid screening of wide areas and supporting near-real-time situational awareness when fused with other BorderForce data sources and workflows. Exploitation relevance is high for border and coast-guard authorities and system integrators because the component can be deployed as an analytics module/service within surveillance and command-and-control environments to cue operators, prioritise investigation, and support evidence-led monitoring. The exploitation route is primarily operational uptake via integration and procurement (as a software component or service), with straightforward reuse in future EU initiatives requiring scalable EO-based object detection.

5.4 Stakeholders and end-users

The exploitation and sustainability of BorderForce results depend on engaging stakeholder groups that influence adoption, validation acceptance, procurement decisions and operational integration. The project context explicitly concerns border surveillance and control, involves border authorities and customs, and addresses multi-authority

collaboration, including cooperation with EU and candidate country authorities and relevant mission contexts.

The stakeholder landscape for exploitation at Month 15 is structured as follows.

Primary operational adopters.

Border guard authorities and customs services are central adopters. For these stakeholders, exploitation is primarily operational uptake and procurement readiness: translation of validated outputs into technical specifications, procurement documentation, training needs and deployment guidance. Authority partners' early inputs highlight the role of technical specification preparation and initiation of procurement processes, and the expectation that project results will support identification and application of suitable solutions.

National ministries and governmental structures.

Relevant ministries (notably ministries of interior and, where applicable, defence-related structures) are key stakeholders influencing adoption and procurement. Industrial partners explicitly identify ministries of interior as primary targets due to their governance role over operational units and their involvement in procurement and policy prioritisation.

European-level stakeholders and cross-border cooperation actors.

European and cross-border stakeholders influence interoperability expectations, replication potential and alignment with broader operational frameworks. These actors matter for exploitation where cross-country interoperability and harmonised approaches are required.

Ethics, privacy, legal and societal stakeholders.

Because BorderForce explicitly emphasises fundamental rights and ethical considerations in border surveillance capability development, stakeholders relevant to ethics, privacy, data protection and social impacts shape exploitation feasibility. This is particularly relevant for analytics, OSINT-based processing and risk-indicator fusion. Exploitable governance measures and mitigation plans strengthen adoption readiness and reduce procurement risk.

Industry, integrators and enabling technology ecosystems.

System integrators and technology providers influence packaging, maintenance and scaling of deployable systems. For these stakeholders, exploitation is typically via integration, licensing, service delivery models and support contracts, depending on how mature and validated the components become.

At Month 15, stakeholder engagement is therefore treated as both a dissemination activity and an exploitation-enabling mechanism: it supports validation relevance, reduces adoption uncertainty, and progressively aligns outputs with procurement and operational priorities.

5.5 Competitor and market landscape

At M15, competitor analysis is necessarily indicative and framed around functional categories rather than final “product-to-product” comparisons. BorderForce combines

deployable command-and-control, sensing, analytics, OSINT processing, user interfaces, training, interoperability design and governance safeguards; competitive pressure may come from both integrated suites and partial substitutes.

Integrated border surveillance suites and fixed infrastructure solutions.

Authorities have existing systems combining cameras, radars, sensors and command software, often procured as integrated packages. These solutions may offer maturity and vendor stability but may not provide the same flexibility and deployability intended by BorderForce. BorderForce's initial differentiation is the ability to support dynamic deployment needs and integrate multiple sources into a deployable concept, with explicit attention to sustainable and rights-aware design.

Counter-UAV and situational awareness platforms.

Dedicated counter-UAV solutions and situational awareness systems can compete with certain BorderForce components (e.g., UAV detection and tracking, operational interfaces). BorderForce must therefore demonstrate the added value of integrated deployment contexts and multi-source fusion within an interoperable architecture, supported by operational feedback.

Communications and resilient networking solutions.

Mesh networking exists across public safety, defence and emergency response sectors. Competitive differentiation is likely to depend on operational suitability, deployability, interoperability and security constraints rather than novelty alone.

OSINT and analytics tooling.

OSINT tools exist commercially and in public-sector ecosystems. BorderForce differentiation is expected to lie in tailoring outputs to border-region threat indicators, integrating them with geo-referenced risk indicators, and embedding governance safeguards appropriate to the border surveillance context.

XR/visualisation and training solutions.

Generic XR and training platforms exist, but BorderForce's differentiation is expected to come from integration with operational workflows and collaborative assessment needs, enabling training that directly supports use of project-developed indicators and interfaces.

This initial landscape indicates that exploitation should focus on the integrated value proposition and evidence from validation activities, rather than treating each component as a standalone market entry at Month 15.

5.6 SWOT analysis

Strengths.

BorderForce addresses an operational need for adaptable surveillance and improved situational awareness in uncertain conditions. The project integrates complementary technological and organisational elements into a coherent deployable concept and includes research, industry and operational authorities, supporting relevance and adoption pathways. The explicit attention to ethical, legal and social considerations strengthens

legitimacy and reduces adoption barriers, particularly for analytics and intelligence-related functions.

Weaknesses.

At Month 15, multiple results are still under development, and comparative advantage cannot yet be evidenced through operational validation outcomes. Dissemination and exploitation are constrained by the sensitivity of border/security capabilities, which limits open communication and requires controlled sharing. In addition, the individual exploitation-plan collection is not yet complete across all partners, reducing the immediate granularity of consortium-wide exploitation planning.

Opportunities.

There is increasing demand for flexible, deployable solutions and for improved data integration, decision support and training approaches. Procurement-oriented outputs (requirements, concept of operations, specifications, tender blueprints and interoperability profiles) provide multiple adoption routes beyond commercialisation. The project's emphasis on sustainability and futureproofing may also support stronger alignment with evolving policy and procurement expectations.

Threats.

Incumbent systems and long-term vendor relationships may reduce willingness to adopt new integrated concepts unless validated benefits are clearly demonstrated. Adoption may be delayed by regulatory, privacy and ethics constraints, especially for OSINT processing and risk-indicator fusion. Interoperability and multi-authority coordination complexity can increase implementation costs and slow procurement cycles. External threat dynamics and policy priorities can also change, requiring continued alignment and stakeholder engagement.

5.7 Preliminary route-to-market and distribution channels

At M15, exploitation planning recognises two main uptake routes, reflecting the different nature of the project results.

Route 1: Technology integration and solution packaging (technical components and software).

For technical KERs (deployable command-and-control, sensing integration, mesh communications, OSINT tooling, risk-indicator fusion, visualisation and training interfaces), the initial route-to-market is based on progressive integration within the BorderForce system and controlled demonstrations to relevant stakeholders. Distribution channels are primarily targeted and relationship-based: direct engagement with border authorities and ministries, controlled demonstrations and technical presentations, and participation in selected practitioner events. Partner inputs confirm the relevance of organisational communication channels (web presence, professional communication channels, press materials and brochures) as supportive dissemination tools, while noting the need to manage confidentiality and sensitivity.

Route 2: Procurement readiness and operational adoption (specifications, governance, requirements, blueprint).

For procurement-oriented and governance KERs (cost-effective and energy-efficient specifications, sustainable recommendations, interoperability profiles, requirements and concepts of operation, tender blueprint, privacy and ethical mitigation, cybersecurity/standards operationalisation), exploitation is expected primarily through authority uptake rather than direct commercialisation. Distribution channels are institutional and practitioner channels: internal adoption within participating authorities, structured sharing with peer institutions, contribution to technical specification drafting, and integration into procurement planning and tender documentation. Authority partner inputs specifically emphasise these mechanisms, including preparation of technical specifications and procurement initiation.

Across both routes, exploitation planning will remain aligned with consortium arrangements on ownership, access rights and controlled dissemination of sensitive information. At Month 15, BorderForce does not yet provide mature business cases for individual technical components, as integration and operational validation are still ongoing. However, for the main technical KERs, partners are recording outline-level business-plan assumptions to guide later exploitation planning. These include early hypotheses on how results could be packaged (standalone module vs integrated capability vs service), what adoption-enabling services are likely to be required (e.g., training, integration support, maintenance), and which adopter profiles are most relevant (authorities, ministries, system integrators). These assumptions are treated as working inputs and will be refined once field validation provides evidence on performance, usability and operational fit. Pre-procurement is a core exploitation route for BorderForce, particularly for results that are expected to be adopted through public-sector procurement rather than standalone commercialisation. At Month 15, these actions remain preparatory and focus on creating a clear path from project outputs to procurement-ready material once validation evidence is available. Phase-1 pre-procurement actions include:

- preparing specification-oriented descriptions of KERs (scope, interfaces, dependencies and deployment constraints);
- linking ConOps and requirements to procurement-relevant language (what capability is needed, under which operational conditions);
- identifying candidate evaluation criteria and evidence needs for later tenders (e.g., performance, interoperability, usability, security/compliance); and
- mapping which outputs are best exploited via procurement documentation (requirements/specifications/blueprints/governance measures) versus which are candidates for modular technical supply (software/component/service).

5.8 Individual exploitation plans collected (baseline at Month 15)

This subsection consolidates the individual exploitation intentions received by Month 15. The plans are indicative and focus on intended results, channels and expected added value rather than achievements.

5.8.1 SECU (Securiton GmbH)

SECU describes an intention to use BorderForce lessons learned to strengthen future capabilities, particularly in relation to deployable command-and-control/tower concepts and counter-UAV deployment contexts. SECU indicates that it can use its networks and associations to distribute outcomes but highlights the sensitivity of the domain and the

need to distinguish clearly between publishable results and information requiring confidentiality. This is relevant for exploitation planning because dissemination and market engagement must be channeled through controlled stakeholder engagement where appropriate.

SECU identifies ministries of interior as primary targets, reflecting the governance structure of many operational units, and also points to other governmental institutions and critical infrastructure operators as potentially relevant stakeholders. Its listed channels include organisational website presence, professional communication channels, press releases, brochures and presentations at selected events. SECU's expected added value is improved alignment of solutions with EU border guard needs (e.g., deployable C2/tower) and learning around deployment contexts that are new for the organisation, complementing already market-proven counter-UAV products.

5.8.2 AIT (AIT Austrian Institute of Technology GmbH)

AIT positions itself as a research institute bridging research and industrial application, with relevant know-how in deployable sensing platforms and on-the-edge AI computer vision as well as mixed-reality planning tools. AIT indicates that its Multi Sensor Prototype Platform will be integrated into the final system and that it plans to further develop and present the platform and associated tools to stakeholders and end users beyond the project, including demonstrations to interested national actors.

AIT's intended exploitable results include the deployable sensing platform, mixed-reality planning software for virtual representation of surveilled areas using geo-referenced indications, and image fake-detection capabilities intended for ministerial contexts. Target stakeholders include border authorities and customs, law enforcement agencies, ministries of defence and private security organisations. Planned channels include selected events, stakeholder demonstrations and licensing of the mixed-reality planning software as part of the platform's uptake. Expected added value is strengthened positioning and contribution to improved situational awareness in border surveillance contexts.

5.8.3 SBGS (State Border Guard Service, Lithuania)

SBGS outlines its statutory responsibilities for protection of Lithuania's land and sea borders and for border checks. It clarifies that it does not have an internal research and development unit and frames exploitation through its operational role: identifying effective solutions, preparing technical specifications and initiating procurement for equipment and implementation services. SBGS expects BorderForce outcomes to provide additional knowledge and support the identification and application of appropriate solutions for effective border protection. This positions SBGS exploitation primarily as operational uptake and procurement readiness, rather than market-oriented commercialisation.

5.8.4 LRM (Lithuanian Customs Department under the Ministry of Finance)

LRM describes its involvement in EU-level coordination and expert groups within its competence and identifies multiple international and European cooperation frameworks as relevant networks. It intends to integrate knowledge and components useful for its activities and expresses readiness to cooperate with SBGS. Planned exploitation actions include presenting results to colleagues in other cooperating institutions and participating

in future demonstrations and trainings. The expected added value relates to identifying solutions to prevent illegal smuggling (in particular cigarettes) and improving monitoring of locations linked to smuggling and other criminal activities.

5.8.5 GSH (Geosystems Hellas)

GSH will exploit the AI-based object detection module for satellite images (optical and SAR) developed in BorderForce, which provides automated detection of objects of interest with bounding boxes and confidence scores and is designed for integration into surveillance and situational-awareness workflows. At the beginning of the project, GSH focused on concrete preparatory actions: producing a short value proposition and factsheet describing the module's capabilities, inputs/outputs and integration approach; engaging an initial set of relevant stakeholders (border/coast guard authorities and system integrators) to capture early feedback on priority object classes and operational needs; and preparing the first demonstrations based on project scenarios and available datasets. In parallel, GSH started dissemination through its own channels (website and professional communication) and by participating in selected EO/security events, while exploring early exploitation routes with potential adopters, primarily procurement-oriented uptake as a software component or service within larger integrated systems.

5.8.6 ED Luxembourg

ED outlines an exploitation strategy centred on maximizing the potential of the Registry of Sensing & External Interfaces Subsystems developed in BorderForce, as well as the customized Collaborative C2 Platform. ED indicates that the registry component represents a reusable and scalable result that can either be transformed into a standalone registry system or integrated into ED's broader platform offerings, addressing interoperability, coordination and secure integration needs in complex civil security and defence environments. In parallel, ED plans to exploit the customized Collaborative C2 System developed within the project by adapting and reusing it in future research initiatives and by commercialising it through licensing models targeted at border authorities, public security bodies and system integrators. The C2 solution is seen as particularly relevant for multi-asset coordination, mission planning and situational awareness use cases, where modularity and compliance with public-sector operational requirements are critical. Beyond specific software components.

ED identifies its primary target markets as national, EU-level and international public administrations and agencies operating in civil security and defence, reflecting its established role as a trusted technology provider to public-sector organisations. Exploitation actions will be channeled through the expansion of ED's existing product and service portfolio. Additional channels include engagement with public organisations already served by ED, structured collaboration with system integrators, and the strengthening of strategic alliances with consortium partners and other global actors. The expected added value for ED lies in the enrichment of its technical capabilities and service portfolio with innovative, market-relevant solutions and increased competitiveness in addressing complex public-sector security needs.

5.8.7 ECoE (ERATOSTHENES Centre of Excellence)

ECoE will exploit the mesh-based communication capability developed in BorderForce, which supports resilient connectivity among deployable assets and distributed sensing elements, including mission scenarios where portable radio nodes may be carried by UAVs to extend coverage and maintain operational communications in infrastructure-limited environments. During the first project period, ECoE's exploitation focus is expected to be primarily integration-driven: consolidating the technical building blocks, documenting operational constraints and performance assumptions emerging from the project use cases, and preparing the first demonstrations of the mesh functionality as part of the integrated BorderForce system rather than as a standalone product. In parallel, ECoE can leverage its role in the Earth observation and digital innovation ecosystem to engage relevant stakeholder communities (e.g., civil protection, public safety and security actors, and system integrators) through targeted workshops, technical exchanges and selected events, while identifying longer-term uptake routes where mesh communications can be reused as an enabling module in future deployments, pilots and procurement-oriented system packages requiring deployable, secure and interoperable connectivity.

5.8.8 VTT

VTT will exploit BorderForce results primarily through the research outputs it leads, notably the Concept of Operations (ConOps), system requirements and pilot definition work that translate technical components into implementable operational concepts aligned with EU priorities and border-security needs. The exploitation activities also include the assessment methodology defined for a comprehensive evaluation of the BorderForce system and its components in industrial and real-life settings. In addition, VTT will further exploit the mobile XR C2 solution by positioning it as a transferable capability for enhancing situational awareness and field-level decision making in future border-security and military systems. In the first project period, VTT's exploitation effort is expected to focus on consolidating and refining requirements and ConOps elements based on iterative consortium inputs, and ensuring that these outputs remain usable as a reference set for future R&I activities in border surveillance and related fields. This also encompasses the adaptation of the assessment methodology for new research and commercial initiatives designed to improve operator situational awareness, particularly those with comparable deployment environments, technologies, and user profiles. This period also includes the early exploitation of the mobile XR C2 concept, especially through validating its operational relevance and integration potential in practitioner workflows. VTT will support exploitation by engaging practitioner communities through research and stakeholder networks and structured dissemination and by positioning the BorderForce ConOps-requirements-assessment methodology as reusable assets that can inform future EU initiatives and national procurement processes, especially where deployability, performance, interoperability and human factors design constraints need to be expressed clearly in operational terms.

5.8.9 HSE

HSE's intended exploitable results include Multimodal Data Fusion, Risk Assessment, and Open-Source Intelligence (OSINT) tools designed to support the integrated analysis of heterogeneous data sources, informed risk evaluation, and enhanced situational

awareness. The target stakeholders comprise research and innovation actors, public and private organisations, and technology providers. Exploitation will be pursued through the use of these tools in research activities, their validation via demonstrations and pilot use cases, and their integration into existing or newly developed solutions and services. The expected added value includes strengthened research outputs, improved decision-support capabilities, and the effective transfer of technological knowledge into practical, scalable, and deployable applications.

5.9 Expected impacts from exploitation (society and stakeholders)

This subsection summarises the expected impacts that BorderForce exploitation can generate, distinguishing short-term (M1–M15 / immediately after RP1) and long-term (post-project) impacts for (i) society and fundamental rights, and (ii) key stakeholder groups. The impacts are consistent with the project’s objective to deliver more flexible, rapidly deployable and cost-/energy-efficient border surveillance capabilities with fundamental-rights protection by design, and with the expected outcomes of the relevant Horizon Europe topic on border surveillance and situational awareness.

5.9.1 Short-term impact on society (M1–M15 and immediately after RP1)

In the short term, BorderForce generates societal impact primarily through improved preparedness and capability development, rather than through deployment at scale. By consolidating deployable surveillance concepts (including transportable C2 stations, resilient connectivity, and multi-source analytics) and aligning them with practitioner needs, the project contributes to more informed and coordinated decision-making in border areas where conditions and threat patterns can change rapidly.

A central short-term societal contribution is the explicit emphasis on ethical considerations and fundamental rights during capability development. This strengthens the legitimacy and acceptability of emerging surveillance approaches by ensuring that privacy and rights-related concerns are recognised early and accompanied by mitigation thinking, rather than treated as a late-stage add-on.

In addition, BorderForce’s early focus on cost-effectiveness, energy efficiency and reduced environmental footprint supports a societal interest in public-sector solutions that are not only operationally effective but also sustainable and responsible in lifecycle terms.

5.9.2 Long-term impact on society (post-project)

In the longer term, exploitation of BorderForce results is expected to contribute to improved security and stability in border regions by enabling more flexible and rapidly deployable surveillance capacity than rigid physical barriers, while supporting the fight against illegal activities across external borders and improving safety of people and operators in border areas.

A key long-term societal impact is the potential to embed fundamental-rights protection by design into border surveillance capabilities, in relevant for analytics and OSINT-based threat assessment, so that future deployments can better balance operational needs with privacy and rights safeguards, thereby improving trust and reducing social friction around border technology use.

Finally, by producing procurement- and governance-relevant outputs (e.g., specifications, interoperability guidance, and sustainability recommendations), BorderForce can contribute to replicable, harmonised adoption across authorities, strengthening cross-border cooperation and reducing fragmentation that can weaken overall security outcomes.

5.9.3 Short-term impact on stakeholders (M1–M15 and immediately after RP1)

For border authorities and customs, short-term impact is expressed through knowledge uptake and procurement readiness: improved understanding of what deployable and interoperable surveillance concepts could look like, and earlier ability to translate needs into technical specifications and procurement planning. This is consistent with the authority partners' stated exploitation approach (specifications and procurement initiation rather than commercialisation).

For ministries and national decision-makers, BorderForce's early stakeholder engagement and structured KER identification support better-informed prioritisation and governance decisions, including how to balance capability enhancement with compliance and sustainability expectations.

For industrial and technology partners, short-term impact is the clarification of productisation and integration direction, including identification of target adopters (e.g., ministries of interior and other governmental bodies) and feasible controlled dissemination channels in a sensitive domain.

For ethics/legal/compliance stakeholders, short-term impact is earlier visibility into risk areas and mitigation approaches, enabling more robust deployment-readiness planning and reducing future adoption barriers.

5.9.4 Long-term impact on stakeholders (post-project)

For border authorities and customs, long-term impact is expected through uptake of validated concepts and procurement-ready assets, supporting more effective and flexible surveillance, improved situational awareness, and safer operations in dynamic border environments.

For European-level cooperation actors and cross-border networks, long-term impact is improved interoperability and compatibility across authorities, enabling joint missions and coordinated responses where operational effectiveness depends on shared situational awareness and data exchange.

For industry and integrators, long-term impact is the potential to integrate validated modules (deployable C2, resilient communications, analytics, visualisation/training) into maintainable solution packages and service offerings aligned with public procurement realities, supported by controlled demonstrations and stakeholder trust built through rights-aware design.

For societal oversight and rights stakeholders, long-term impact is strengthened governance capability: clear mitigation measures and operational practices that can be referenced in procurement, deployment guidelines and accountability processes, helping adoption proceed with fewer legal/ethical obstacles and higher public trust.

5.10 Next steps for exploitation consolidation (M16–M30)

In M16–M30, exploitation work will focus on completing and refining of individual exploitation plans across the full consortium, refining the KER list as integration progresses, and strengthening exploitation positioning based on evidence from validation activities and stakeholder feedback. This refinement will be informed by integration results and evidence from the Bulgaria and Lithuania field trials. The preliminary stakeholder mapping, competitor landscape and route-to-market logic will be updated accordingly, and procurement-oriented assets (requirements, specifications, interoperability profiles, governance measures and blueprint elements) will be elaborated to improve adoption readiness and sustainability after project end.

6 OUTLINE OF STANDARDISATION PLAN

6.1 Introduction

6.1.1 Purpose

The purpose of this document is to present the initial Standardisation Plan for the BorderForce project and to establish a coherent framework for coordinating, prioritising, and implementing standardisation activities across all technological components developed under Work Packages 3, 4 and 6. As BorderForce introduces innovative capabilities, including deployable C2 infrastructure, multi-sensor intelligence fusion, drone-based surveillance, AI-powered OSINT analytics, XR-enhanced situational awareness, and a federated GIS-driven mission-planning platform, standardisation becomes essential to ensure interoperability, security, transparency, and long-term sustainability of the project's outcomes.

This deliverable outlines how BorderForce will align its technical developments with relevant European and international standardisation ecosystems (including CEN/CENELEC, ISO, IEEE, ITU, OGC, and ETSI), contributing to ongoing initiatives where appropriate and identifying gaps where project innovations may inform future standards. It provides a consolidated view of the standardisation landscape, defines the principles guiding the project's engagement with standards-developing organisations, and specifies the expected interactions, timelines, and responsibilities of each partner.

Furthermore, the document sets the foundation for the project's exploitation and dissemination activities by ensuring that BorderForce technologies are designed in accordance with existing or emerging standards, thereby maximising their potential for adoption by EU Member States, border-management authorities, industry stakeholders, and other security practitioners. It will be updated throughout the project to reflect evolving standardisation needs, ensuring continued alignment with regulatory requirements, interoperability expectations, and the broader innovation objectives of Horizon Europe.

6.1.2 Scope

This document defines the scope of the BorderForce Standardisation Plan and delineates the boundaries within which the project's standardisation activities will be designed, executed, and monitored. Its primary focus is to translate the technical developments of Work Packages 3 and 4, covering deployable C2 infrastructure, multi-source sensing, AI-enhanced intelligence processing, XR-based human-machine interaction, mesh communications, geospatial interoperability and risk-assessment capabilities, into a coherent set of standardisation priorities that support interoperability, operational reliability, cross-border adoption, and long-term sustainability of the BorderForce solution.

The scope of the document includes: (i) a comprehensive mapping of relevant European and international standards, standardisation committees, and ongoing work items; (ii) an assessment of how BorderForce technological components align with existing frameworks and where gaps exist; (iii) the identification of specific working groups within CEN, CENELEC, ISO, IEEE, ITU, ETSI, and OGC that are relevant to BorderForce's innovations; and (iv) the definition of partner responsibilities, expected contributions, engagement

modalities, and timelines for participation throughout the project duration. The analysis integrates inputs from the project's Description of the Action, especially the technical objectives described in Annex 1 of the Grant Agreement, ensuring that standardisation efforts directly support the development, integration and validation activities envisaged for the achievement of TRL7 by the end of the project.

Furthermore, the document sets the foundation for the project's subsequent communication, dissemination, exploitation and innovation activities (as outlined in WP6) by establishing how BorderForce will position its results within the broader European security and border-management standardisation ecosystem. Elements outside the scope of this document include detailed descriptions of the underlying technologies themselves, market analysis, regulatory compliance procedures, and exploitation strategies, which are addressed in complementary deliverables. Instead, the focus remains on the strategic and operational framework enabling BorderForce to contribute meaningfully to the evolution of standards in border surveillance, sensor interoperability, AI safety, geospatial data exchange, and operational situational awareness.

6.2 Standardisation Approach and Methodology

BorderForce integrates a diverse set of technologies, ranging from mobile C2 infrastructure and interoperable sensor networks to AI-driven risk assessment, XR operational tools, satellite–drone fusion, OSINT analytics, and secure mesh communications, each situated within established or emerging European and international standards. To ensure interoperability, security, trustworthiness, and long-term adoption of project results across Member States and border-management authorities, it is essential that standardisation activities follow a structured and proactive methodology. This section outlines the overarching approach that guides how BorderForce identifies relevant standards, aligns innovations with them, and contributes to standardisation bodies across the project lifecycle.

The methodology builds on three pillars: (i) landscape mapping and alignment, ensuring BorderForce technologies comply with and leverage existing standards; (ii) targeted engagement, enabling partners to participate in committees, working groups, and consultations; and (iii) contribution and impact, identifying where BorderForce can shape emerging standards or provide use cases, best practices, or data models that can inform ongoing work. Activities follow a cyclical process throughout the project: initial mapping, continuous monitoring, gap identification, engagement planning, and impact assessment.

This approach ensures compliance with the obligations of Horizon Europe projects, such as promoting interoperability, contributing to European technological sovereignty, and supporting the EU's strategic position in AI, security, and digital transformation, while leveraging opportunities within CEN/CENELEC, ISO, ITU, ETSI, IEEE, OGC, and other relevant standardisation ecosystems.

6.2.1 Objectives of Border-Force Standardisation Activities

The standardisation activities of BorderForce pursue a set of strategic, technical, and operational objectives aimed at ensuring that the project's results are robust, interoperable, and suitable for long-term operational use by EU border authorities, customs agencies, and CSDP entities. These objectives are informed by the technology areas described in Work

Packages 3 and 4 and by the broader mission outlined in the Grant Agreement, which emphasises cross-border collaboration, privacy-preserving intelligence methods, and secure, real-time operational awareness across the EU's external borders.

Objective 1: Ensure interoperability across heterogeneous systems and platforms

BorderForce integrates stationary, mobile and aerial sensors, OSINT data sources, crowdsourced information streams, drones, satellites, and mesh network endpoints into a unified C2 and mission-planning environment. A central objective is therefore to align data structures, interfaces, communication protocols, metadata models, and visualisation standards with existing international frameworks such as ISO 191xx for geospatial data, OGC standards for sensor and geospatial interoperability, IEEE protocols for wireless/mesh networking, and evolving CEN/ETSI work on drones, resilience, and security operations. Achieving interoperability reduces integration costs, simplifies adoption for public authorities, and supports cross-border data exchange during emergencies or joint missions.

Objective 2: Promote trust, transparency, and responsible use of AI and intelligence technologies

The project includes advanced analytics, AI-based OSINT, cross-modal fusion, real-time threat scoring, and automated alerting. Standardisation activities will align these components with emerging standards on trustworthy AI (CEN-CLC JTC 21), robustness and transparency (ISO/IEC 42001 series), explainability and risk management (ISO/IEC 23894, IEEE 7000 series), and misinformation/deepfake detection efforts. This ensures that BorderForce technologies not only meet ethical and legal expectations but can be validated, audited and integrated into operational workflows by border authorities in compliance with EU values and rights-based frameworks.

Objective 3: Strengthen security, resilience, and reliability of communications and data exchanges

Border surveillance operations depend on continuous, secure and resilient communication, whether through mesh networks, 5G links, satellite relays, or drone-based communication nodes. Standardisation objectives include alignment with ISO/IEC 27000-series cybersecurity standards, ETSI security requirements, ITU recommendations for UAV communications, and risk-management standards such as ISO 31000. Establishing secure-by-design interfaces and cryptographic practices early in the project supports the safe deployment of BorderForce technologies during field trials and future operational uptake.

Objective 4: Contribute to emerging standards for novel BorderForce technologies

Some BorderForce innovations, such as multi-UAV cooperative sensing, cross-domain fusion, XR operational interfaces, or specialised mission-planning ontologies, operate in areas where standards are still evolving or missing. The project therefore seeks to contribute evidence, use cases, pilot data, and best practices to committees such as ISO/TC 20/SC14/WG8 (downstream space services), ETSI ISG ARF (augmented reality), or OGC working groups. Contributions may take the form of liaison partner inputs, draft CEN Workshop Agreements, white papers, or participation in testbeds.

Objective 5: Support exploitation and long-term adoption of BorderForce solutions

Alignment with recognised standards accelerates uptake by LEAs, procurement authorities, and operational units. Throughout the project, standardisation efforts will be integrated with dissemination, communication and exploitation planning (WP6) to ensure that BorderForce outputs remain compatible with EU procurement frameworks and can be certified, benchmarked, or validated through established methodologies.

6.2.2 Methodology

The BorderForce standardisation methodology is designed as a continuous, iterative process that runs in parallel with the technical work of Work Packages (WPs) 3 and 4 and the communication, dissemination and exploitation activities in WP6. It combines top-down analysis of the existing standardisation landscape with bottom-up inputs from pilots, prototypes and end-user validation, ensuring that the project both complies with relevant standards and actively contributes to their evolution.

The methodology is organised into six interlinked phases:

1. Landscape Mapping & Scoping
2. Technology–Standards Mapping & Gap Analysis
3. Planning of Engagement & Contributions
4. Execution of Standardisation Activities
5. Monitoring, Feedback & Iteration
6. Integration with Dissemination, Exploitation and Policy

Each phase is described in detail below.

6.2.2.1 LANDSCAPE MAPPING & SCOPING

In the first phase, the consortium establishes a shared understanding of the standardisation environment relevant to BorderForce technologies. This is based primarily on:

- The Standardisation Roadmap for BorderForce Technology Areas, which identifies key committees, workshops and initiatives in CEN, CENELEC, ISO, IEEE, ITU, ETSI, OGC and related bodies for each technical capability (C2 station, OSINT toolkit, satellite–drone fusion, sensor registry, data fusion, mesh networking, XR tools, WebGIS mission planning).
- The Grant Agreement Annex 1, which defines the action’s objectives, work packages, tasks and planned TRL7 validation through two field trials.

Activities in this phase include:

- Identification of relevant SDOs and groups
 - e.g. CEN/WS COURAGEOUS, CEN/TC 471, ISO/TC 20/SC14/WG8, ISO/TC 211, ISO/TC 262, ISO/TC 292, CEN-CLC JTC 21, ETSI ISG ARF, ETSI ISG SAI, IEEE 7000 series, OGC Defence & Intelligence DWG, ITU-T SG20, etc.
- Review of existing standards and work items relevant to drones/UAS, geospatial data, IoT, AI, XR, risk management, security and resilience, mesh communications, and emergency information exchange.
- Prioritisation of domains according to:
 - Direct relevance to BorderForce components and pilots.

- Strategic importance for EU security and border-management policy.
- Openness of participation (preference for open or easily accessible WGs/workshops).

The result of this phase is an initial standards catalogue, structured per technology area and reused later as Annex A of the deliverable.

6.2.2.2 TECHNOLOGY-STANDARDS MAPPING & GAP ANALYSIS

In the second phase, the consortium performs a detailed mapping between BorderForce technical artefacts and relevant standards, as already outlined thematically in the Standardisation Roadmap.

For each key subsystem (T3.1–T3.4, T4.1–T4.4), the methodology foresees:

1. Functional decomposition
 - a. Breaking down each BorderForce capability into its functional blocks, e.g.:
 - i. Smart C2 Station: power subsystem, edge-computing platform, UAV integration interface, c-UAS RF detection module, etc.
 - ii. OSINT Toolkit: data collection layer, NLP/vision analytics, misinformation detection, ethics and privacy safeguards.
 - iii. Fusion & Risk Module: data ingestion, fusion engine, risk model, CIRAM-based output formats.
2. Standards alignment tables
 - a. For each function/interface, link to specific standards (e.g. ISO 19115 for metadata, OGC SensorThings for sensor APIs, IEEE 802.11s for mesh routing, ISO 31000 for risk management, ETSI ARF reference architecture for XR, etc.).
 - b. Capture the type of relationship:
 - i. Compliance required (e.g. interoperability with EUROSUR formats, as far as disclosed).
 - ii. Recommended alignment (e.g. applying ISO/IEC AI management guidelines).
 - iii. Inspirational (e.g. using ETSI ARF use cases as design guidance).
3. Gap analysis
 - a. Identify areas where:
 - i. No suitable standard exists (e.g., drone swarms operational doctrines, standardised deepfake detection benchmarks, XR interfaces for C2 in border operations).
 - ii. Existing standards are too generic and would benefit from security/border-oriented profiles, e.g. an OGC profile for cross-border mission-planning GIS.
 - b. Document these gaps as opportunities for contribution, forming the basis of later CWA proposals, white papers or liaison inputs.

Outputs from this phase are:

- A set of technology–standards mapping tables (to be included in Annex C).
- A consolidated Gap & Opportunity Report, which feeds into the planning phase.

6.2.2.3 PLANNING OF ENGAGEMENT & CONDITIONS

The third phase translates the identified needs and gaps into a concrete engagement plan with SDOs and WGs, taking into account the project's timeline (30 months), reporting periods and pilot schedule.

Key elements include:

1. Assignment of responsibilities per partner and per SDO/WG
 - a. For each priority committee or workshop, a “responsible partner” and one or more “supporting partners” are designated. Examples (to be detailed in Section 7):
 - i. SECU → CEN/WS COURAGEOUS, CEN/TC 471 (UAS/c-UAS).
 - ii. GSH/ECoE → ISO/TC 20/SC14/WG8, OGC DWGs (space and geospatial).
 - iii. ED → OGC APIs, ISO/TC 211, CEN/TC 391, OASIS EDXL.
 - iv. Eticas/HSE → CEN-CLC JTC 21, ISO/IEC AI standards, IEEE 7000.
 - v. VTT/AIT → ETSI ISG ARF, OpenXR, XR safety standards.
2. Definition of engagement modalities
 - a. Participation in national mirror committees (for CEN/CENELEC and ISO).
 - b. Direct participation in workshops and industry specification groups (e.g. ETSI ISG ARF, OGC testbeds, Metaverse Standards Forum activities related to XR).
 - c. Contribution to consultations, questionnaires, public reviews of draft standards.
 - d. Preparation of BorderForce use cases, white papers, technical notes to be submitted to relevant WGs.
3. Alignment with project phases
 - a. Early phase (M1–M12): focus on landscape validation, initial alignment, and identification of quick wins (e.g. ensuring geospatial data formats follow OGC/INSPIRE from the first prototypes).
 - b. Mid-project (M13–M24): emphasise concrete contributions, based on intermediate prototypes and internal evaluations, including participation in testbeds and workshops.
 - c. Final phase (M25–M30): document lessons learned from field trials, produce standardisation-oriented outputs (e.g. profiles, recommendations, CWA proposals) and integrate them into exploitation packages.

The output of this phase is an SDO Engagement Plan and Calendar, which is later refined into Section 7 (Standardisation Roadmap) with milestones and KPIs.

6.2.2.4 EXECUTION OF STANDARDISATION ACTIVITIES

In the fourth phase, the project performs the actual standardisation work, according to the engagement plan. This includes both inbound alignment (adapting BorderForce design to standards) and outbound contributions (informing and shaping standards).

Inbound alignment activities include:

- Incorporating relevant standards into architecture and design documents for the C2 station, sensor registry, mesh network, data fusion engine, OSINT toolkit, XR tools and GIS platform.
- Using standard data models and interfaces (e.g. OGC SensorThings, ISO 191xx, EDXL CAP messages) in the implementation of communication and data flows.
- Applying AI, security, privacy and ethics standards as non-functional requirements, ensuring solutions remain compliant with EU legislation and values.

Outbound contribution activities include:

- Providing BorderForce use cases, requirements and operational scenarios to standardisation groups (e.g. c-UAS test scenarios, satellite-drone fusion in border areas, XR-assisted mission planning).
- Submitting comments and proposed enhancements during public review of draft standards or reports (e.g. CEN workshop agreements, ETSI group specifications).
- Participating in testbeds, plugtests and proof-of-concepts organised by OGC, ETSI or others, using BorderForce components as demonstrators.
- Preparing joint position papers or white papers with other EU projects and practitioner organisations, highlighting the need for specific profiles or guidelines (e.g. multi-source risk fusion in alignment with CIRAM).

All execution activities are documented in standardisation activity logs, which capture date, SDO/WG, type of contribution, responsible partner and follow-up actions. These logs support internal coordination and serve as evidence for project reporting.

6.2.2.5 MONITORING, FEEDBACK & ITERATION

The fifth phase ensures that standardisation remains a living process throughout the project:

1. Regular monitoring and updates
 - a. WP6 (or the designated standardisation lead) organises periodic reviews (e.g. every 6 months) where partners report:
 - i. New or updated standards relevant to their components.
 - ii. Progress on engagement actions (meetings attended, inputs submitted).
 - iii. Changes in SDO roadmaps that affect BorderForce (e.g. new work items in AI, XR, or drone regulations).
2. Feedback into technical work
 - a. Changes in standards or new guidelines are fed back into system design, implementation, and pilot configuration through WP3 and WP4 technical meetings.
 - b. Conversely, issues encountered in pilots (e.g. interoperability problems, limitations of existing standards in real border environments) are recorded and turned into feedback recommendations for relevant WGs.
3. Risk and issue management
 - a. Standardisation-related risks (e.g. closed committees, delays in standard publication, conflicting requirements) are monitored in the project risk register.
 - b. Mitigation measures may include:

- i. Participation via national bodies;
- ii. Seeking alternative open fora (e.g. OGC, IEEE, Metaverse Standards Forum);
- iii. Preparing internal guidelines that can later be “packaged” as potential standards when the ecosystem is ready.

This feedback loop ensures that standardisation activities remain aligned with project realities and policy developments rather than static or purely theoretical.

6.2.2.6 INTEGRATION WITH DISSEMINATION, EXPLOITATION AND POLICY

The final phase of the methodology focuses on mainstreaming standardisation outputs into broader project impacts:

- Integration with communication and dissemination (WP6):
 - Standardisation achievements (e.g. new profiles, contributions to CWAs, participation in testbeds) are highlighted in public deliverables, project website, policy briefs and conference presentations.
 - Where appropriate, workshops or side events are organised jointly with SDOs or other EU projects to showcase BorderForce as a reference implementation of open, standards-based border surveillance.
- Integration with exploitation and innovation planning:
 - Standard-compliant architectures and interfaces become explicit selling points for future commercialisation or follow-on deployments by industry partners.
 - Exploitation plans reference the standards landscape to show how BorderForce solutions can be procured, integrated and maintained by border authorities and customs agencies using existing frameworks.
- Policy relevance:
 - Insights from standardisation work (e.g. gaps identified, needs for specific cross-border data models) are fed into policy recommendations and position papers targeting EU bodies, agencies and Member State authorities.
 - This strengthens the link between BorderForce, the EU policy agenda on integrated border management and the strategic objective of reinforcing Europe’s role in setting global standards for security technologies.

Through these six phases, the methodology ensures that standardisation is systematic, documented, and tightly coupled with the technical development, validation and exploitation of BorderForce results, thereby maximising scientific, operational and policy impact.

6.3 Standardisation Landscape per Technology Area

This section provides a structured examination of the standardisation landscape relevant to the technological building blocks developed under Work Packages 3 and 4 of the BorderForce project. As outlined in the Grant Agreement and further detailed in the project's Standardisation Roadmap, BorderForce integrates a broad spectrum of technologies—including deployable C2 infrastructure, interoperable sensor networks, satellite–drone fusion, AI-based OSINT, multimodal data fusion, mesh communications, XR-assisted interfaces, and WebGIS-based mission planning—each of which is deeply interconnected with existing or emerging European and international standards.

The purpose of this section is to analyse, for each of these technology areas, the current state of standardisation, the relevant standards bodies and working groups, and the opportunities for BorderForce to both implement and influence technical standards. By understanding this landscape, the consortium can ensure that the project's components are aligned with recognised frameworks, support interoperability across borders and agencies, and contribute effectively to the future evolution of standards in security, AI, geospatial information, resilience, and human–machine interaction.

The landscape is organised around the major subsystems of BorderForce. For each subsystem, the analysis includes:

- **Technical Description and Relevance:** A concise summary of the subsystem's role in the BorderForce architecture and its relevance for field operations and TRL7 validation.
- **Relevant Standards-Developing Organisations (SDOs):** Identification of the key European and international bodies—such as CEN, CENELEC, ISO, IEC, IEEE, ITU, ETSI, OGC, OASIS and others—that publish or maintain standards applicable to the subsystem.
- **Existing Standards and Ongoing Work Items:** Overview of current standards, technical reports, and active working groups that provide design constraints, interoperability requirements, best practices, or emerging specifications.
- **Gaps and Needs for New Standardisation Efforts:** Highlighting areas where current standards are insufficient or absent, particularly in domains such as drone–satellite collaboration, multimodal fusion for border security, explainable and trustworthy AI for real-time decision-making, XR-enhanced situational awareness, and cross-border mission-planning ontologies.
- **Potential BorderForce Contributions:** Opportunities for the project to inform standardisation efforts through technical feedback, use cases, testbeds, white papers, liaison participation or proposals for new CEN Workshops or OGC profiles.

The following subsections explore the standardisation landscape for each major technology area in detail, establishing the foundation for the engagement activities and contributions presented in the Standardisation Roadmap.

6.3.1 Deployable Smart C2 Station & Edge Sensing

The Deployable Smart C2 Station is a core component of the BorderForce architecture, designed to provide a self-sufficient, rapidly deployable, and interoperable operational node capable of supporting multi-domain sensing, autonomous analytics, and local

command-and-control functions. As described in WP3 and Annex 1 of the Grant Agreement, the C2 Station integrates configurable surveillance towers, edge-computing modules, communication relays, anti-drone capabilities, and interfaces for UAV platforms, allowing border authorities to maintain situational awareness even in remote, infrastructure-poor environments.

Given its modular and multi-technology nature, the Smart C2 Station intersects with several standardisation domains, including unmanned aircraft systems (UAS), sensor interoperability, wireless communications, security and resilience frameworks, and wide-area surveillance systems. The following subsections summarise the relevant SDOs, existing standards, active work items, and opportunities for Border Force contributions, as identified from their publicly available web resources.

Relevant Standards-Developing Organisations

The primary SDOs associated with T3.1 include:

- CEN / CENELEC
 - CEN/TC 471 – Focused on standards for unmanned aircraft systems, including conformance and interoperability guidelines relevant to UAV docking, detection, and coordination with C2 nodes.
- ISO
 - ISO/TC 20/SC 16 – Covers unmanned aircraft systems, including specifications for communication links, command and control, geofencing, and interoperability.
 - ISO/TC 20/SC 14/WG 8 – Downstream space services with relevance for integration of satellite imagery and telemetry into C2 operations. BorderForce is already planning participation in WG8, which is explicitly prioritised in the roadmap.
 - ISO/TC 211 – Geospatial information standards (e.g. ISO 19115 for metadata, ISO 19157 for data quality) relevant for structuring sensor outputs consumed by the C2 Station.
- IEEE
 - Standards for:
 - Wireless LAN & mesh networks (IEEE 802.11s)
 - Ad-hoc networking and routing
 - Cyber-physical systems and IoT interoperability
 - These inform the communication modules of the C2 Station and its integration with mesh networking platforms from WP4.
- ITU
 - ITU-R UAV communication and spectrum guidelines, especially for safe operation of drones in proximity to fixed or mobile C2 infrastructure.
 - ITU-T SG20 – Standards for IoT and smart environment deployments, relevant for sensor gateway interoperability.
- ETSI
 - ETSI TR 103 850 – Specifications related to UAS for public safety and border security operations.
 - ETSI ISG SAI – AI security standards relevant for on-edge analytics.

Existing Standards and Ongoing Work Items

Relevant existing standards include:

- ISO 21384 series for UAS operations, interoperability, command and control.
- ISO 191xx series for metadata, geospatial structuring and data formats for C2 integration.
- OGC SensorThings API and SensorML, providing standardised structures for sensor description, observations, metadata, and tasking capabilities.
- IEEE 802.11s for mesh network routing, used when the C2 Station acts as a communication relay.

Active and emerging work items relevant to BorderForce include:

- ISO/TC 20/SC 16 WG drafts on enhanced UAS operational safety requirements and extended-range data link protocols.
- ETSI activities focused on integrating 5G/NR communications with autonomous surveillance systems.

These developments directly inform the design of the Smart C2 Station, particularly in ensuring safe UAV operations, legitimate c-UAS detection, and standardised sensor and communication interfaces.

Gaps and Needs for New Standardisation Efforts

Despite extensive activity in the domain, several gaps remain where BorderForce innovations can provide significant value:

1. Edge-based multi-sensor fusion for border surveillance: No standard currently defines on-site fusion models for combining radar, RF, thermal, optical, acoustic and UAV data streams at the edge. BorderForce's implementation can inform future guidance.
2. Interoperability profiles for mobile C2 stations: Existing standards address fixed or aviation-grounded infrastructure, but there is no common profile for rapidly deployable, modular C2 units that integrate drones, sensors and mesh networks in the context of border missions.
3. Counter-UAS integrated protocols: While CEN/WS COURAGEOUS provides testing guidelines, interoperability standards between c-UAS sensors and C2 platforms are not formalised.
4. Field-operational constraints: Standards do not sufficiently account for harsh terrain, fluctuating power conditions, or degraded connectivity—typical in border surveillance environments.
5. Metadata harmonisation for multi-domain assets: There is no unified metadata framework spanning drones, ground sensors, satellites, and C2 logs in border management scenarios.

These gaps represent high-impact opportunities for evidence-based contributions from BorderForce based on field trials and prototype evaluations.

Potential BorderForce Contributions

BorderForce can contribute to standardisation across several dimensions:

- Provision of operational use cases for deployable C2 stations in remote border environments (to CEN, ISO, OGC WGs).
- Technical feedback on standards for UAS interoperability, particularly regarding coordinated operations between drones and mobile C2 units.
- Performance data from field trials to inform metrics for sensor-to-C2 latency, reliability, and environmental resilience.
- Profiles or recommendations for integrating c-UAS detection systems into modular surveillance towers.
- Drafting or supporting new CEN Workshop Agreements focusing on multi-sensor C2 integration and mobile surveillance infrastructure.
- Participation in ISO/TC 20/SC 14/WG 8, contributing insights on satellite downstream data fusion into tactical C2 systems.

Through these activities, BorderForce ensures that its Smart C2 Station is built upon solid standardisation foundations while simultaneously contributing to the evolution of standards in Europe and internationally.

6.3.2 AI-based OSINT Toolkit

The AI-based OSINT Toolkit is a core analytical component of BorderForce, designed to collect, process, classify and interpret large volumes of publicly available online information—including text, imagery, social media content and other digital traces—to support early detection of threats, situational awareness and intelligence-led decision making. As specified in WP3 and in Annex 1 of the Grant Agreement, the OSINT Toolkit contributes to the assessment of border security risks by identifying emerging events, behavioural indicators, misinformation patterns, or cross-border criminal activities that may signal operational concerns. The OSINT Toolkit sits at the intersection of AI, cybersecurity, digital content provenance, trustworthiness, ethical data processing and security intelligence frameworks, making its standardisation landscape particularly dynamic. The following subsections analyse the relevant SDOs, standards, work items, identified gaps and potential areas where BorderForce can contribute.

Relevant Standards-Developing Organisations

Several major European and international SDOs are actively developing standards related to AI, data quality, content integrity, misinformation detection, OSINT workflows and security intelligence.

- CEN / CENELEC
 - CEN-CLC JTC 21 – Artificial Intelligence: Developing European standards aligned with the EU AI Act, focusing on trustworthy AI, transparency, robustness, risk classification and conformity assessment.
- ISO / IEC
 - ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 42 – Artificial Intelligence: Covers foundational and advanced AI standards, including:
 - ISO/IEC 22989 (AI concepts and terminology)
 - ISO/IEC 23053 (AI system framework)

- ISO/IEC 23894 (AI risk management)
- ISO/IEC 42001 series (AI management systems)
- ISO/TC 292 – Security and Resilience: Relevant for intelligence-gathering methodologies and threat information management.
- ISO/IEC 27000 series: Provides security controls for data processing, integrity, provenance and information security management systems.
- IEEE
 - IEEE 7000 Series (Ethical AI Guidelines)
 - IEEE 7001 (Transparency), 7003 (Algorithmic Bias), 7004 (Child and Vulnerable Protection), and 7010 (Well-being metrics) are directly relevant to ethical OSINT operations.
 - IEEE P3119 (Deepfake Detection) – Emerging standard on synthetic media identification.
- ETSI
 - ETSI ISG SAI (Securing Artificial Intelligence): Defines vulnerabilities, threats and countermeasures for AI systems used in security contexts.
- ITU
 - ITU-T SG17 (Security) – Includes work on cybersecurity, digital trust and content authenticity.
 - ITU/UNESCO Focus Groups on AI & Truth – Address misinformation ecosystems and digital content verification.

These SDOs together shape the emerging regulatory and technical framework for OSINT-driven analytics in Europe.

Existing Standards and Ongoing Work Items

The OSINT Toolkit must align with several existing standards:

AI and Algorithmic Governance

- ISO/IEC 23894 – Risk management for AI systems.
- ISO/IEC 42001 – Requirements for an AI management system (AIMS).
- IEEE 7000 series – Ethical design processes for AI.
- ETSI SAI publications – Threat taxonomy, security risks and mitigations for AI algorithms.

Ongoing standards development activities

- ISO/IEC TR 27557 & 27559 on AI explainability and transparency.
- ISO/IEC 5259 series on data quality for analytics and machine learning.
- ITU-T “AI for Good” initiatives on combating online harms.

These ongoing developments provide early opportunities for BorderForce to test applicability and provide formal feedback.

Gaps and Needs for New Standardisation Efforts

Despite substantial activity across SDOs, gaps remain that directly affect OSINT operations for border management:

1. Lack of operational OSINT standards for real-time border security: Current standards focus on cyber intelligence or general information analysis, but none provide harmonised workflows, ontologies or data schemas specifically suited for border surveillance and cross-border threat analysis.
2. Absence of standard benchmarks for misinformation, disinformation and harmful online content detection: Deepfake detection and synthetic media provenance standards are still in early development, with no unified datasets or performance metrics widely accepted.
3. Ethical and legal OSINT operations in EU security missions: Though addressed in part by the IEEE 7000 series and ISO/IEC SC42 ethics guidelines, there is no EU-specific standard defining privacy-preserving OSINT practices for border authorities.
4. No common interoperability framework for OSINT–C2 integration: Existing geospatial and sensor standards (ISO 191xx, OGC) do not fully cover:
 - OSINT-to-fusion-engine data flows,
 - Confidence scoring models,
 - Intelligence validation metadata.
5. Lack of standardised explainability models for risk-scoring systems: While emerging work exists in SC42, there is no operationalised explainability model tailored for high-stakes decisions such as border security alerts.

These gaps present clear areas for contributions from BorderForce, especially through operational validation, use-case definition and real-world data-driven insights.

Potential BorderForce Contributions

BorderForce can provide substantial value to standards communities through:

1. Use cases and requirements for OSINT in border security

Real-world operational scenarios from practitioner partners (border police, customs, maritime authorities) can inform CEN, ISO, and ITU working groups on:

- a. Information flow models
 - b. Ethical constraints
 - c. Reliability and confidence annotation
 - d. Integration with C2 and mission planning
2. Feedback on emerging AI and content authenticity standards

By testing OSINT models on real operational data, BorderForce can offer input on:

- a. Explainability requirements

- b. Bias mitigation workflows
 - c. Model robustness to adversarial content
 - d. Deepfake detection performance
3. Support for EU-driven trustworthy AI efforts

BorderForce can contribute to:

- a. CEN-CLC JTC 21 technical specifications,
- b. ISO/IEC SC42 feedback cycles,
- c. ETSI SAI reports,

ensuring AI systems used in border surveillance comply with the EU's emerging risk-based AI governance framework.

4. Participation in CEN/WS SMCD refinements

BorderForce's multi-language, multi-modal OSINT processing methods can support updates to cyber-intelligence methodologies, especially for:

- a. Fact verification
- b. Cross-platform content correlation
- c. Threat pattern identification

5. Recommendations for a future "OSINT Interoperability Profile"

Based on project outcomes, BorderForce may propose:

- a. A CEN Workshop Agreement (CWA)
- b. An OGC Discussion Paper
- c. Or an ISO Technical Report

focusing on interoperable OSINT data models, metadata and ethical safeguards for border-management use cases

6.3.3 Satellite-Drone Sensing & Swarm Intelligence

The Satellite-Drone Sensing and Swarm Intelligence component of BorderForce (T3.3) integrates heterogeneous aerial and space-based assets into a unified intelligence framework, enabling persistent monitoring, high-frequency revisit capabilities, and coordinated drone operations to support border surveillance missions. As outlined in the Description of the Action (Annex 1), BorderForce leverages EO satellite constellations, CubeSat-derived imagery, fixed-wing and multirotor UAVs, and distributed onboard AI processing to deliver real-time situation awareness, detect anomalous activities, and coordinate tactical responses in remote border areas. This subsystem relies on both mature EO standards and rapidly evolving drone/swarms standards, while also exposing significant gaps, particularly in areas where the standardisation ecosystem has not yet caught up with emerging multi-agent autonomous systems. Below, we examine the relevant SDOs,

existing standards and ongoing initiatives, as well as the standardisation gaps and opportunities for BorderForce contribution.

Relevant Standards-Developing Organisations

- ISO
 - ISO/TC 20 – Aircraft and Space Vehicles
 - SC 14 – Space Systems and Operations
 - WG 8 – Downstream Space Services (explicitly highlighted in the Standardisation Roadmap for BorderForce participation). This group addresses EO data delivery models, metadata structures, quality frameworks and interoperability aspects for satellite imagery used in security operations.
 - SC 16 – Unmanned Aircraft Systems: Covers UAV safety, operational requirements, communication interfaces, detect-and-avoid capabilities and remote ID.
 - ISO/TC 211 – Geographic Information / Geomatics: Provides the foundation for standardised geospatial data representations essential for integrating satellite imagery and UAV-derived products.
- OGC – Open Geospatial Consortium
 - OGC plays a central role in EO and UAV data interoperability:
 - OGC SensorML – Sensor description models.
 - OGC SensorThings API – Standard interfaces for sensor data ingestion.
 - OGC EO Profiles & OGC API – EDR (Environmental Data Retrieval) – Relevant for delivering actionable satellite analytics.
 - OGC Testbeds exploring Earth observation fusion, UAV integration and 3D geospatial data, all relevant for BorderForce's multi-sensor pipeline.
- CEN / CENELEC
 - CEN/TC 471 – UAS – Unmanned aircraft system standards that influence drone operational envelopes, safety and integration with ground infrastructure.
 - Potential relevance for mission-critical systems through CENELEC safety and dependability groups.
- ITU – International Telecommunication Union
 - ITU-R – Standards for UAV command-and-control links, spectrum allocation and interference management.

- ITU-T SG20 – IoT and smart environment standards, relevant when UAVs function as mobile sensing platforms.
- IEEE
 - Standards in:
 - Cooperative robotics and autonomous systems (IEEE 1872 ontology for robotic systems).
 - UAV communication protocols.
 - Emerging work in multi-robot coordination and swarm interoperability.
- ESA / Copernicus (Not formal SDOs but de facto standard-setters): Provide widely adopted EO data models, metadata schemas and access protocols, indirectly influencing standardisation landscapes.

Existing Standards and Ongoing Work Items

- Earth Observation and Geospatial Standards
 - ISO 19115 / 19115-2 – Metadata for geographic information and imagery.
 - ISO 19130 – Sensor models for EO systems.
 - OGC GeoTIFF, OGC WMS/WCS/WFS, and OGC API – Processes – Core standards for imagery ingestion, tiling and retrieval.
 - OGC STAC (SpatioTemporal Asset Catalog) – Widely used for structuring EO datasets (not a formal ISO/OGC standard yet, but rapidly becoming a de facto industry standard).

These standards ensure interoperability of satellite-derived data across BorderForce components.

- Unmanned Aircraft Systems
 - ISO 21384 series – Baseline UAS operational and safety requirements.
 - ISO/TS 23665 – Training requirements for UAS operations.
 - Remote ID & UAS traffic management (UTM) – Evolving standards in SC 16 and ICAO groups, essential for ensuring safe drone operations in proximity to border infrastructures.
- Swarm and Multi-UAV Coordination
 - There are currently no mature international standards defining:
 - Interoperability protocols for swarm coordination.
 - Standard communication schemas for autonomous mission sharing among UAVs.

- Multi-agent decision-making or behaviour models for swarms in security contexts.
- Some emerging activities include:
 - IEEE RA (Robotics & Automation) exploratory work items on multi-robot coordination.
 - OGC interoperability experiments involving drone fleets.
 - NATO STO work (not an SDO but influential) on multi-UAV ISR frameworks.

BorderForce is uniquely positioned to contribute to conceptual, architectural and operational foundations for these emerging areas.

Gaps and Needs for New Standardisation Efforts

1. Drone–Satellite Fusion Standards: While EO and UAV standards exist separately, no integrated standard defines:
 - a. How drone imagery, satellite imagery and ground sensors should be fused.
 - b. How metadata from different platforms should be harmonised.
 - c. How temporal and spatial inconsistencies should be represented.
2. Swarm Intelligence and Multi-UAV Tasking: No standards define:
 - a. Swarm communication interoperability.
 - b. Shared situational awareness models.
 - c. Collaborative task allocation for UAV fleets.
 - d. Ethical and safety constraints for semi-autonomous multi-agent systems.

The lack of frameworks for trust, accountability and explainability in swarm decision-making creates a major gap.

3. Edge-AI on UAVs and Satellites: Current standards only superficially address:
 - a. Onboard inference reliability.
 - b. Compression of models for edge execution.
 - c. Federated learning across UAV fleets.
 - d. AI lifecycle and auditing for flying platforms.
4. Operational Protocols for Persistent Surveillance: EO standards define data; UAS standards define aircraft behaviour; but no combined standard exists for persistent surveillance missions using heterogeneous aerial assets.
5. Security and Resilience: There is no unified standard covering:
 - a. Secure UAV-satellite-ground communication triads.

- b. Cyber-resilience of multi-UAV systems.
- c. Jamming or spoofing resistance for distributed reconnaissance.

These gaps are directly relevant to BorderForce’s innovation goals and represent high-impact opportunities for contribution.

Potential BorderForce Contributions

BorderForce can significantly influence the direction of international standards through:

1. Participation in ISO/TC 20/SC 14/WG 8: The consortium's operational use cases involving satellite-supported border security are uniquely suited to inform standards on:
 - a. EO downstream services for security.
 - b. Harmonisation of UAV–EO data models.
 - c. Quality metrics for multi-source aerial surveillance.
 2. Contribution to OGC Testbeds and DWGs: BorderForce can propose:
 - a. A UAV–Satellite Fusion Profile for disaster response and border monitoring.
 - b. Enhancements to SensorML and SensorThings for representing multi-UAV metadata.
 - c. Demonstrations of UAV-satellite fusion workflows.
 3. Recommendations for Swarm Intelligence Standardisation: Through field trials and prototyping, BorderForce can generate early technical evidence needed to shape:
 - a. Swarm communication schemas.
 - b. Mission-sharing protocols.
 - c. Behavioural and safety constraints for autonomous multi-UAV systems.
- BorderForce may also lead or contribute to a future CEN Workshop Agreement (CWA) on Interoperable Multi-UAV Systems for Border Surveillance.
4. Insights for ITU and IEEE on UAV Communications: BorderForce’s operational environments provide valuable data on:
 - a. RF propagation in remote border areas.
 - b. Robustness requirements for UAV–ground links.
 - c. Cooperative mesh networking with UAV nodes.
 5. Ethical, Privacy and Safety Considerations for Aerial Intelligence Systems
 - a. Partner expertise (e.g., Eticas) can support the development of guidelines addressing:
 - i. Responsible AI on UAVs.

- ii. Minimisation of over-surveillance risks.
- iii. Transparency requirements for semi-autonomous aerial missions.

6.3.4 External Data Integration & Sensor Registry

The External Data Integration and Sensor Registry component (T3.4) is responsible for enabling BorderForce to ingest, harmonise, store, describe and manage a wide range of heterogeneous data sources, including ground sensors, UAV payloads, satellite feeds, OSINT streams, environmental sensors, third-party data services and legacy surveillance systems used by border authorities. As described in Annex 1 of the Grant Agreement, the objective of T3.4 is to establish a scalable and semantically coherent sensor and data integration layer, ensuring interoperability across components, enabling federated data access, and providing uniform application interfaces for downstream modules such as multimodal fusion, risk assessment and mission planning.

This subsystem is deeply embedded in geospatial standards, sensor metadata frameworks, IoT interoperability, and secure data exchange standards. Its successful implementation ensures that BorderForce technologies can integrate with existing national infrastructures, EU-level situational awareness platforms and future border-management systems.

Relevant Standards-Developing Organisations

The key SDOs shaping the landscape for external data integration and sensor registry include:

- OGC – Open Geospatial Consortium: OGC provides the most relevant standards for describing, cataloguing and serving sensor observations and geospatial resources:
 - OGC SensorThings API – A RESTful standard widely adopted for IoT sensor data.
 - OGC SensorML – Standardised sensor metadata describing capabilities, calibration, processes and provenance.
 - OGC Observations & Measurements (O&M) – Conceptual model for observations and results.
 - OGC Catalogue Service (CSW) / OGC API Records – Search and discovery of geospatial resources.
 - OGC API family (Features, Tiles, Processes, EDR) – Modern, web-native endpoints for federated geospatial data access.

Given the multi-sensor nature of BorderForce, OGC standards form the backbone of the sensor registry design.

- ISO
 - ISO/TC 211 – Geographic Information: Includes foundational standards for spatial data structures, metadata (ISO 19115), quality (ISO 19157), schemas (ISO 19109) and cataloguing (ISO 19110).

- ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 41 – Internet of Things and Digital Twin: Focuses on IoT interoperability models, architecture frameworks and device lifecycle management, relevant for field sensors and edge nodes.
- ISO 19156 (Observations and Measurements): Provides conceptual grounding for structuring sensor observations.
- CEN / CENELEC
 - CEN/TC 391 – Societal and Citizen Security: Addresses interoperability frameworks and structured information exchanges in security operations.
 - CEN/CLC JTC 13 – Cybersecurity and Data Protection: Defines requirements for secure data exchange, data integrity, encryption and identity management.
- OASIS
 - EDXL (Emergency Data Exchange Language)
 - EDXL-DE, EDXL-SitRep, EDXL-CAP (Common Alerting Protocol)

These standards support structured information sharing in emergency and crisis environments and may support integration with national/regional emergency coordination systems.

- ITU
 - ITU-T SG20 – IoT and Smart Cities: Develops frameworks supporting IoT devices, interoperability and secure information exchange.

These SDOs define the standards that will enable BorderForce to act as a federated, multi-source intelligence platform with consistent data structures and interfaces.

Existing Standards and Ongoing Work Items

The sensor registry and integration layer must align with several mature standards:

- Geospatial Metadata & Structuring
 - ISO 19115 / 19115-2 – Metadata for geographic information and imagery.
 - ISO 19157 – Data quality for geospatial resources.
 - ISO 19111 – Referencing by coordinates.
- Sensor Metadata and Observations
 - OGC SensorML – Descriptive metadata for sensors.
 - OGC Observations & Measurements (O&M) – Conceptual model used by SensorThings and other sensor frameworks.
 - OGC SWE Common Data Model – Standard structures for encoding sensor data.
- APIs, Catalogues and Interoperable Services

- OGC SensorThings API Part 1 & 2 – Interoperable patterns for IoT devices and tasking.
- OGC API – Features / Tiles / EDR / Processes – Modular standards for spatial and environmental data.
- CSW 3.0 / OGC API – Records – For discoverability of data resources within federated systems.
- Emerging Work Items
 - OGC Testbeds on cross-domain sensor fusion, federated catalogues, and UAV data integration.
 - ISO/IEC SC 41 work on IoT device lifecycle governance, semantic interoperability and edge computing architectures.
 - CEN/CLC JTC 13 work on secure data exchange in distributed security architectures.
- BorderForce can leverage these maturing frameworks to ensure long-term compatibility with national and EU-level systems.

Gaps and Needs for New Standardisation Efforts

Despite the maturity of geospatial and sensor-related standards, several gaps remain where BorderForce innovation exceeds current standardisation maturity:

1. Unified Metadata for Heterogeneous Sensors in Border Environments. Existing standards are strong for single-domain sensors, but not for:
 - a. Multi-sensor towers combining radar, RF, acoustic, optical, thermal, AIS, ADS-B, etc.
 - b. UAV-mounted modular sensor packages.
 - c. Satellite products with variable temporal/spatial resolutions.
 - d. A unified metadata model tailored to border surveillance ecosystems does not exist.
2. Cross-Platform Sensor Discovery and Orchestration. While OGC provides catalogue standards, there is no:
 - a. Cross-domain registry for aerial, terrestrial, maritime and space sensors,
 - b. Standard protocol for dynamic sensor onboarding/offboarding in tactical deployments.
3. Real-Time Fusion-Oriented Data Models. Standards describe observations but do not define:
 - a. Time-aligned, fusion-ready data schemas.
 - b. Confidence, uncertainty or provenance structures suitable for high-stakes risk assessment.

4. Federated Security Requirements. Existing cybersecurity standards do not fully address:
 - a. Sensor authentication in degraded communication settings,
 - b. Secure data exchange between mobile C2 units, UAVs and cloud nodes,
 - c. Distributed trust frameworks for heterogeneous sensor sources.
5. Integration with Border-Specific Intelligence Systems. There is a standardisation gap between sensor frameworks (ISO/OGC) and:
 - a. Intelligence models (CIRAM used by Frontex),
 - b. Operational situational awareness systems used by border agencies.

BorderForce's work is uniquely suited to addressing these gaps.

Potential BorderForce Contributions

BorderForce can contribute meaningfully to advancing the state of standardisation in this domain:

1. Development of a Unified Sensor Metadata Framework for Border Operations. A harmonised metadata model covering:
 - a. Platform type (fixed, mobile, UAV, satellite),
 - b. Sensor characteristics,
 - c. Operational parameters,
 - d. Geolocation and calibration,
 - e. Data provenance and quality metrics.

This could evolve into:

- f. A CEN Workshop Agreement,
 - g. An OGC Best Practice document,
 - h. Or a Technical Report under ISO/TC 211.
2. Participation in OGC Testbeds and DWGs. BorderForce can support:
 - a. Interoperability experiments for UAV-centric geospatial workflows,
 - b. Validation of SensorThings for high-frequency border surveillance applications,
 - c. Prototyping federated catalogue services for operational monitoring.
3. Promotion of Standardised Fusion-Ready Data Schemas. By documenting the data paths between:
 - a. Sensors,
 - b. The Sensor Registry,

- c. The Fusion and Risk Assessment Components (WP4),
- BorderForce can propose structured schemas incorporating:
- d. Confidence scores,
 - e. Explainability metadata,
 - f. Cross-modal alignment structures.
4. Contributions to Cybersecurity and Resilience Standards. Experience from operating distributed sensors in harsh and connectivity-limited environments can inform:
 - a. CEN/CLC JTC 13,
 - b. ISO/IEC 27033 (network security architecture),
 - c. Emerging ITU recommendations for secure IoT deployments.
 5. Operational Use Cases for Federated Sensor Networks. BorderForce field trials provide:
 - a. Real operational datasets,
 - b. Extreme-environment scenarios,
 - c. Multinational interoperability requirements.

These insights are highly valuable to SDOs and can drive new standardisation initiatives.

6.3.5 Multimodal Fusion, AI Reasoning & Risk Assessment

The Multimodal Fusion, AI Reasoning and Risk Assessment component (T4.1) lies at the core of the BorderForce decision-support architecture. It transforms heterogeneous inputs—ranging from satellite imagery, drone video, ground sensor data, geospatial layers, OSINT-derived signals, environmental data and operator annotations—into harmonised situational intelligence and actionable early-warning indicators. As outlined in Annex 1 of the Grant Agreement, this subsystem implements advanced fusion models, cross-modal reasoning engines and automated risk scoring aligned with European border-management frameworks such as CIRAM (Common Integrated Risk Analysis Model).

Given its AI-centric nature and its role as the analytical "brain" of the system, T4.1 intersects with numerous ongoing standardisation efforts related to AI trustworthiness, explainability, multimodal analytics, risk modelling, security and resilience, data quality, information exchange and operational intelligence frameworks. This section presents the standardisation landscape governing this subsystem, identifies gaps, and highlights areas where BorderForce can contribute to shaping emerging standards.

Relevant Standards-Developing Organisations

The primary SDOs relevant to multimodal fusion and risk assessment include:

- ISO / IEC

- ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 42 – Artificial Intelligence
The leading international committee defining foundational and advanced standards for AI systems, including:
 - AI terminology, taxonomies and architectures (ISO/IEC 22989; 23053)
 - Risk management (ISO/IEC 23894)
 - Bias mitigation and transparency
 - Data quality for analytics (ISO/IEC 5259 series)
 - AI management systems (ISO/IEC 42001 series)
- ISO/TC 262 – Risk Management Governs generic risk management principles applicable across domains, forming a basis for BorderForce’s structured approach to threat evaluation.
- ISO/TC 292 – Security & Resilience Covers emergency management, information sharing and resilience standards relevant to threat evaluation and response coordination.
- CEN / CENELEC
 - CEN/CLC JTC 21 – Artificial Intelligence Focused on European AI standardisation aligned with the EU AI Act. Work includes conformity assessment, trustworthy AI, documentation requirements, transparency measures and operational guidelines for high-risk AI systems.
- ETSI
 - ETSI ISG SAI – Securing Artificial Intelligence Addresses vulnerabilities, threat taxonomies, secure AI lifecycle management, robustness against adversarial attacks and resilience of AI pipelines.
 - ETSI ISG CIM – Context Information Management Supports interoperability of contextual and semantic information—a key requirement for multimodal fusion.
- OGC – Open Geospatial Consortium

Responsible for standards on geospatial encoding, spatial-temporal alignment, and 3D situational models, which are essential for fusing and contextualising observations from aerial, terrestrial and space-based assets.

- ITU
 - ITU-T Focus Groups on AI for Good & Trustworthy AI Address explainability, transparency and ethical use of AI in public safety and crisis management contexts.
- Frontex / EU Agencies Frameworks (Non-SDO but highly influential)

- CIRAM 2.0 methodology Provides a conceptual and procedural baseline for risk assessment in EU border-management operations and is explicitly referenced in the Grant Agreement as a guiding model for BorderForce’s risk-scoring components.

Existing Standards and Ongoing Work Items

- AI Governance and Risk Management
- ISO/IEC 23894 – AI risk management, defining risk assessment principles and mitigation approaches.
- ISO/IEC 23053 – Framework for AI systems using machine learning.
- ISO/IEC 42001 series – AI management systems ensuring robust governance.

These are foundational for the design of BorderForce’s fusion and reasoning components.

- Data Quality & Multimodal Analytics
- ISO/IEC 5259 – Data quality for analytics and machine learning.
- ISO 19157 – Geospatial data quality, relevant when combining GIS layers with sensor-derived inputs.
- OGC standards for spatial-temporal encoding, critical for harmonising drone, satellite and ground sensor data.
- Explainability & Transparency

Several emerging SC42 work items address:

- Explainability metrics for AI models,
- Traceability of AI decision-making,
- Documentation requirements for high-risk AI systems (aligned with the EU AI Act).

These efforts are crucial for ensuring BorderForce’s risk-scoring engine is transparent, accountable and legally compliant.

- Security and Robustness
 - ETSI SAI threat and risk models Provide taxonomies for vulnerabilities in AI pipelines, which are directly applicable to multimodal fusion models used in real-time monitoring.
 - ISO/IEC 27032, 27035 and 27001 Support secure data processing, incident handling and information security management.

Gaps and Needs for New Standardisation Efforts

Despite progress in AI standardisation, several critical gaps remain relevant to BorderForce:

1. Lack of standards for multimodal sensor–intelligence fusion. Existing standards cover individual data modalities (e.g., geospatial, sensor streams, OSINT), but there is no cross-modal fusion schema defining:

- a. Alignment of heterogeneous evidence,
- b. Temporal/spatial normalisation,
- c. Fusion confidence metrics,
- d. Semantic interoperability across domains.

BorderForce’s fusion engine can provide early models and schemas for such standards.

2. Absence of operational explainability models for high-stakes AI. While explainability standards exist conceptually, no tailored operational framework exists for:
 - a. Border security risk indicators,
 - b. Multi-stage reasoning chains in surveillance AI,
 - c. Confidence and uncertainty propagation across fusion pipelines.
3. CIRAM-aligned AI risk assessment standards. No international standard currently integrates:
 - a. CIRAM’s structured risk analysis principles,
 - b. Machine-learning-based early-warning indicators,
 - c. Operational risk scoring for border surveillance missions.

BorderForce is one of the first EU-funded projects implementing CIRAM-aligned, multi-source, AI-enhanced risk modelling, placing the consortium in a strong position to inform future standards.

4. Limited standards for adversarial robustness in multimodal AI. ETSI SAI provides general taxonomies, but there are no detailed guidelines for:
 - a. Multi-modal adversarial scenarios,
 - b. Spoofing or jamming attacks affecting spatial and sensor fusion,
 - c. Data poisoning across heterogeneous sensor networks.
5. Ethical and privacy-preserving fusion frameworks. Standards focus largely on data protection and AI fairness, but not on:
 - a. Use of privacy-preserving OSINT within fusion engines,
 - b. Ethical constraints on multi-sensor tracking and identification,
 - c. Recording and auditing of reasoning steps.

Potential BorderForce Contributions

BorderForce can contribute at several levels:

1. Definition of Multimodal Fusion Schemas & Data Models

- a. Standardised representation for fused intelligence objects,
 - b. Cross-modal uncertainty,
 - c. Provenance and explainability annotations. These could underpin a future OGC Best Practice or an ISO/IEC Technical Report.
2. Contribution to AI Governance and Explainability Standards. BorderForce prototypes can provide real-world input to:
- a. ISO/IEC SC 42 work on explainable AI,
 - b. CEN-CLC JTC 21 work on conformity and documentation for high-risk AI systems,
 - c. ETSI SAI work on vulnerability mitigation.
3. CIRAM-Oriented Risk Assessment Guidelines. BorderForce can document use cases, data models and practical lessons learned from integrating CIRAM principles into AI-driven risk engines. This could support:
- a. A CEN Workshop Agreement,
 - b. A Technical Specification, or
 - c. An EU policy guideline for risk-based border surveillance.
4. Contribution to Security and Resilience Communities. BorderForce field trials in operationally challenging environments (remote borders, degraded networks) offer valuable evidence for:
- a. AI robustness requirements,
 - b. Incident response standards for AI systems,
 - c. Best practices for secure multimodal decision-making.
5. Interoperability with External Systems. BorderForce can define mapping templates and interoperability guidelines between:
- a. Sensor registry outputs,
 - b. Fusion engine inputs,
 - c. External border/intelligence systems such as national C2 platforms and practitioner tools used in EU Member States.

These contributions will help shape the future of standards for integrated, trustworthy, and interoperable AI systems deployed in security and border-management domains.

6.3.6 Mesh Communications Network

The Mesh Communications Network developed under T4.2 provides the communication backbone for the BorderForce system, enabling resilient, decentralised, multi-hop data exchange between fixed C2 stations, mobile units, UAVs, and distributed sensors across remote and challenging border environments. As outlined in Annex 1 of the Grant

Agreement, this subsystem ensures that operators and autonomous components can reliably exchange situational awareness information even in areas without fixed telecom infrastructure or where network disruptions occur.

The Mesh Network supports **ad hoc connectivity, dynamic routing, fault tolerance, and scalability**, while integrating multiple communication technologies (Wi-Fi, LTE/5G, MANET protocols, and potentially satellite relays). Standardisation is central to ensuring interoperability with other components, secure coordination of multi-node topologies, and alignment with evolving standards for mission-critical communications.

Relevant Standards-Developing Organisations

- IEEE: IEEE provides foundational standards for wireless networking, ad hoc communications, and routing protocols, including:
 - IEEE 802.11s – Mesh networking amendment defining MAC layer multi-hop forwarding.
 - IEEE 802.15.4 – Low-power mesh networking (applicable for sensor cluster extensions).
 - IEEE 1609 WAVE – Secure, multi-channel communication in dynamic environments.

These standards influence the mesh architecture and its behaviour in rapidly changing topologies.

- IETF – Internet Engineering Task Force: IETF defines the protocols commonly used in MANET (Mobile Ad hoc Network) and wireless mesh architectures, including:
 - AODV / AODVv2 – Reactive routing protocols.
 - OLSR / OLSRv2 – Proactive optimised link-state routing.
 - RPL – Low-power and lossy networks, useful for sensor clusters.
 - DTLS, IPsec, TLS 1.3 – Security building blocks for encrypting transport and application layers.

IETF standards are essential for ensuring routing reliability, avoiding fragmentation, and supporting hybrid mesh–infrastructure communication models.

- 3GPP: For the integration of mobile broadband:
 - 3GPP Release 15–18 – 5G New Radio (NR) capabilities, relevant especially for UAVs and hybrid C2 configurations.
 - 3GPP MCX (Mission Critical Services) – Though not fully adopted by BorderForce, provides insights into interoperable mission-critical voice, data and video.
- ETSI
 - ETSI TS 103 636 (MCX series) – Mission critical communication guidelines.
 - ETSI EN 303 204 – Spectrum access and dynamic spectrum management.

- ITU
 - ITU-T SG13 – Future networks, including aspects of self-managed networks.
 - ITU-R – Spectrum allocation and interference management guidelines essential for UAV integration with mesh nodes.

These SDOs collectively ensure that the BorderForce mesh network aligns with global best practices for ad hoc and mission-critical communications.

Existing Standards and Ongoing Work Items

- Mesh Networking Protocols & Wireless Standards
 - IETF OLSRv2 and AODVv2 – Improved routing specifications with better scalability and performance.
 - Mobile Broadband Integration
 - 3GPP releases introducing:
 - UAV support enhancements,
 - Network slicing for critical communications,
 - Improved handover procedures for dynamic multi-hop environments.
- Security Standards
 - IETF DTLS/TLS 1.3, IPsec, and IEEE 802.11i – Security layers for protecting multi-hop network traffic.
 - ISO/IEC 27033 – Network security architecture guidance.
 - ETSI TC Cyber standards for secure network operation.
- Emerging Work Items
 - IETF MANET analytics for routing optimisation.
 - IEEE work on mesh-assisted UAV communication.
 - ETSI task forces on non-terrestrial networks (NTN) that may influence future UAV-mesh hybrid architectures.

BorderForce's dynamic, UAV-enhanced mesh architecture aligns closely with these emerging initiatives.

Gaps and Needs for New Standardisation Efforts

Despite significant progress, several gaps remain where BorderForce provides unique insights:

1. UAV-Assisted Mesh Networking. While mesh networking and UAV communications have established standards separately, no standards define UAVs as dynamic mesh relays, addressing:
 - a. Adaptive altitude-based link optimisation,

- b. Autonomous route repair via UAV repositioning,
 - c. Dual-role UAVs (sensor + communication node).
2. Mission-Critical Mesh Networking in Remote Border Environments. Standards do not capture:
 - a. Harsh terrain constraints,
 - b. Interference from natural obstacles,
 - c. Long-range mesh links needed for border deployments,
 - d. Degraded connectivity and autonomous self-healing mechanisms.
3. Interoperability Profiles for Hybrid Mesh–C2 Architectures. Existing standards lack:
 - a. Profiles for mobile C2 units interacting with MANETs,
 - b. Interoperability with legacy law-enforcement comms systems,
 - c. Integration points for EO/UAV/sensor data within networks.
4. Network Resilience Under Threat Conditions. Standardisation gaps exist around:
 - a. Resilience against jamming/spoofing,
 - b. Dynamic trust establishment in ad hoc networks,
 - c. Prioritisation of risk-related data during congestion.
5. Quality-of-Service (QoS) Models for Fusion-Driven AI Systems. There is no standard defining:
 - a. Latency and bandwidth requirements for multi-sensor fusion,
 - b. Real-time streaming from drones via mesh paths,
 - c. Confidence and integrity propagation across communication chains.

BorderForce field trials are in an ideal position to provide data-driven recommendations to close these gaps.

Potential BorderForce Contributions

BorderForce can meaningfully influence standards in the following areas:

1. UAV-Assisted Mesh Networking Use Cases & KPIs. By documenting UAV-supported mesh operations in real border conditions, BorderForce can:
 - a. Contribute to IEEE and IETF work on UAV–mesh integration,
 - b. Provide operational KPIs (latency, stability, throughput, resilience).
2. Hybrid Mesh–C2 Interoperability Profiles. The project can propose a CEN Workshop Agreement or OGC Best Practice describing how:
 - a. Mobile C2 stations interact with ad hoc mesh networks,

- b. Data from sensors/UAVs is transported consistently across mesh layers,
 - c. Distributed intelligence systems share risk indicators over unreliable networks.
3. Network Resilience Recommendations. Insights from BorderForce’s pilot deployments can contribute to:
 - a. ETSI TC Cyber guidelines for resilient field networks,
 - b. ISO/IEC 27033 enhancements related to dynamic ad hoc networks,
 - c. ITU recommendations on interference-resistant communication frameworks.
4. Standardised QoS Requirements for Multimodal AI Systems. BorderForce can define:
 - a. Latency thresholds for fusion-driven risk engines,
 - b. Bandwidth requirements for live drone video/imagery,
 - c. Synchronisation needs for multi-sensor streams.
5. Security & Trust Frameworks for Distributed Mesh Nodes. The project can inform:
 - a. Approaches to decentralised authentication,
 - b. Lightweight cryptographic procedures for mesh nodes,
 - c. Trust models adapted to rapidly changing topologies.

These insights could feed into IETF, ETSI and ISO committees working on secure and adaptive communication systems.

6.3.7 XR/MR Situational Awareness Tools

The XR/MR Situational Awareness Tools developed under T4.3 aim to enhance operational decision-making by providing immersive, context-rich visualisations of the BorderForce operational environment. These interfaces allow operators to explore fused intelligence, interact with 3D geospatial representations, visualise real-time sensor feeds, and access mission-critical overlays through augmented, mixed or extended reality systems. As outlined in Annex 1 of the Grant Agreement, XR solutions will support border-control officers in complex missions by enabling intuitive interaction with spatial information, multi-sensor observations and risk indicators.

Given the novelty and rapid evolution of XR technologies—and the specific safety, usability and interoperability needs of security and border-management contexts—standardisation plays an essential role in ensuring that XR tools are reliable, safe, interoperable across devices, and fully compatible with existing and emerging human–computer interaction frameworks. This section examines the relevant standardisation landscape, identifies existing standards, highlights gaps, and outlines potential contributions BorderForce can provide.

Relevant Standards-Developing Organisations

- ETSI – European Telecommunications Standards Institute: ETSI plays a major role in XR standardisation, particularly through:
 - ETSI ISG ARF (Augmented Reality Framework) Defines a reference model and functional components for AR systems, including device capabilities, content formats, interaction methods and interoperability between AR services. The Standardisation Roadmap highlights ARF as a priority area for BorderForce participation due to its relevance for mission-critical XR applications.
- ISO / IEC
 - ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 24 – Computer Graphics, Image Processing and Environmental Data Representation Develops standards for:
 - Virtual, augmented and mixed reality environments,
 - 3D graphics,
 - Animation frameworks,
 - XR ergonomics and safety requirements.
 - ISO 9241 (Ergonomics of Human–System Interaction) Provides principles for visual displays, interaction techniques, usability evaluation and operator well-being—highly relevant for XR systems deployed in operational environments.
 - ISO/IEC 18040 series (XR Safety) – Addresses physical safety, motion tracking and human factors in XR deployments.
- IEEE
 - IEEE 1589 VR/AR/MR)
 - P2048.1 – AR system architecture,
 - P2048.5 – Environmental safety considerations,
 - P2048.7 – Interaction and user interface guidelines,
 - P2048.10 – Performance metrics for XR systems. These standards inform XR display quality, latency, user interaction and system reliability.
- Khronos Group (Industry Consortia – Not an SDO but highly influential)
- OpenXR – A widely adopted cross-platform XR interoperability standard enabling XR applications to run consistently across different hardware devices. BorderForce solutions that adopt OpenXR increase compatibility and reduce hardware dependencies.
- ITU
 - ITU Focus Groups on the Metaverse and Immersive Media Address interoperability, security and accessibility of immersive environments, indirectly supporting XR deployments.

Existing Standards and Ongoing Work Items

- Interoperability and Architecture
 - OpenXR 1.0+ – Provides a unified API layer for XR devices, ensuring consistent behaviour across hardware ecosystems.
 - ETSI GR ARF 009 (AR Framework) – Defines system requirements, rendering models, content management and functional blocks for AR systems.
 - ISO/IEC 14772 / 19775 (VRML / X3D) – Foundational standards for representing 3D scenes and objects.
- Usability, Ergonomics and Safety
 - ISO 9241 series – Human–system interaction principles guiding XR user interface design.
 - ISO/IEC 18040 series – XR safety principles including fatigue, motion sickness, field of view, tracking accuracy and environmental safety requirements.
 - IEEE P2048.x work items – Performance benchmarks, latency requirements, environmental detection and user comfort standards.
- Content Exchange and Rendering
 - glTF (Khronos) – Standard for efficient 3D model delivery; relevant for XR-based geospatial visualisation.
 - OpenGIS standards (OGC) – Used when mapping 3D geospatial content into XR visual interfaces.
- Emerging Work Items
 - XR operational safety for field environments,
 - Multi-user XR collaboration standards,
 - Real-time streaming into XR spaces,
 - Integration of AI-derived insights into XR visual overlays.

These emerging areas are particularly relevant for BorderForce’s immersive representation of fused intelligence.

Gaps and Needs for New Standardisation Efforts

Despite these advances, several gaps remain in XR standardisation, especially in relation to security and field operations.

1. XR for Security & Border-Management Operations. No specific standards exist for:
 - a. Visualising threat indicators,
 - b. Representing fused multi-sensor intelligence in XR,
 - c. Handling classified or sensitive information in immersive environments.

2. Operational Safety in Harsh Field Environments. Existing XR safety standards focus primarily on consumer or industrial use, not:
 - a. Outdoor deployments,
 - b. Environments with extreme weather,
 - c. Low-visibility conditions,
 - d. Risk of physical hazards during XR use.
3. Interoperability with C2 and Mission-Planning Systems. While XR systems are progressing toward platform interoperability via OpenXR, there are no standards for interfacing XR tools with command-and-control (C2) systems, sensor registries, or mission-planning frameworks.
4. Real-Time Integration of Live Sensor Streams. There is no standard for:
 - a. Displaying live drone video feeds in XR,
 - b. Synchronising sensor observations with immersive maps,
 - c. Switching between 2D/3D operational layers during live missions.
5. Cognitive Load and Human Factors for XR in Security Tasks. XR deployments in high-stress, time-critical missions raise unique ergonomic issues not covered by existing usability standards.
6. Ethical and Privacy Considerations. No dedicated standards define:
 - a. How XR systems should handle personal data,
 - b. How fused intelligence overlays should avoid unintentionally identifying individuals,
 - c. How to safeguard sensitive operational information in immersive environments.

These gaps create opportunities for BorderForce to contribute through evidence, prototypes and field validation.

Potential BorderForce Contributions

1. Operational Use Cases for XR in Border Security. BorderForce can provide critical real-world scenarios that can inform ETSI ARF, ISO/IEC SC24 and IEEE P2048 committees on the design and requirements of XR tools used in:
 - a. Rapid threat recognition,
 - b. Mission planning,
 - c. Patrol route optimisation,
 - d. Multi-sensor intelligence exploration.
2. XR Content Models for Multimodal Intelligence. The project can propose:
 - a. 3D symbology for border operations,

- b. A unified spatial-temporal UI model,
- c. XR-specific metadata for fused sensor-intelligence representations.

These could evolve into:

- d. OGC Best Practices,
 - e. An ETSI ARF technical report, or
 - f. A CEN Workshop Agreement (CWA).
3. Interaction Guidelines for XR in High-Stakes Environments. BorderForce can contribute insights on:
- a. Minimising cognitive load,
 - b. Reducing distraction during missions,
 - c. Interaction techniques for cold weather, gloves, or harsh conditions. These findings are relevant to ISO 9241 and IEEE P2048.
4. Security & Privacy Recommendations for Immersive Systems. BorderForce's experience can inform:
- a. Secure data-handling guidelines for XR systems,
 - b. Access control and redaction models for immersive environments,
 - c. Techniques for privacy-preserving overlays.
5. Validation of XR Safety Standards for Outdoor Operations. Field trials will produce valuable operational evidence on:
- a. Physical risks,
 - b. User fatigue,
 - c. Environmental limitations,
 - d. Situational awareness trade-offs.

These insights can support updates to ISO/IEC XR safety frameworks.

6.3.8 Collaborative GIS-Based Mission Planning Platform

The Collaborative GIS-Based Mission Planning Platform developed under T4.4 forms a central operational layer within the BorderForce architecture, enabling end-users to visualise multi-source intelligence, plan missions, coordinate patrol deployments, evaluate risks, and manage operational workflows in real time. As outlined in Annex 1 of the Grant Agreement, the platform integrates geospatial datasets, fused sensor observations, drone and satellite outputs, environmental information, mission history logs, and interactive communication features within a single interface designed to support coordination between border-control teams.

This subsystem relies extensively on geospatial, data-exchange, and situational-awareness standards to ensure interoperability with existing national systems, EU-level frameworks,

and other BorderForce subsystems (e.g., sensor registry, fusion engine, XR interfaces). Standardisation is therefore fundamental to achieving seamless integration, cross-border cooperation, and long-term reusability of the platform.

Relevant Standards-Developing Organisations

- OGC – Open Geospatial Consortium

OGC provides the dominant standards for geospatial data, mapping services, spatial analysis, and sensor integration. Relevant standards include:

- OGC Web Map Service (WMS) – Delivery of 2D map layers.
- OGC Web Feature Service (WFS) – Retrieval of vector feature data.
- OGC Web Coverage Service (WCS) – Access to raster and EO datasets.
- OGC API – Features / Maps / Tiles / Processes / EDR – Modern, RESTful successors to legacy OGC web services.
- CityGML / 3D Tiles – Models for 3D geospatial representation.
- OGC GeoPackage – Container format for portable geospatial data.
- OGC SensorThings & SOS – Federated sensor data integration.

OGC standards form the backbone of interoperable GIS-driven operations.

- ISO
 - ISO/TC 211
 - Geographic Information Foundational standards such as:
 - ISO 19115 / 19115-2 – Metadata,
 - ISO 19111 – Coordinate reference systems,
 - ISO 19117 – Visualisation,
 - ISO 19157 – Data quality,
 - ISO 19119 – Service architecture.

These standards ensure coherence and interoperability across all geospatial information used in the platform.

- CEN / CENELEC
 - CEN/TC 391 – Societal and Citizen Security Provides structured guidance on information exchange, interoperability frameworks, and the use of spatial information in crisis and security management.
- EDXL (Emergency Data Exchange Language) provides standardised message formats for situational alerts, resource management, and operational information exchange, relevant for collaborative mission planning.
- Frontex and EU Systems (Non-SDO but influential)

- CIRAM, EUROSUR data models and conceptual frameworks influence how risk information, alerts, and operational statuses should be visualised and exchanged. *These do not constitute formal standards but shape EU interoperability expectations.*

Existing Standards and Ongoing Work Items

- Geospatial Data & Web Services
 - OGC API – Features / Tiles / Processes / EDR – Modern standards for delivery, filtering and interaction with spatial data.
 - OGC WMS, WFS, WCS – Widely deployed standards for map and data services.
 - GeoPackage – Platform-independent data containers for offline and mobile use.
- 3D and Real-Time Visualisation
 - CityGML, OGC 3D Tiles, I3S – Standards for multi-scale 3D representations, relevant for terrain, border infrastructures and situational overlays.
 - ISO 19117 (Portrayal) – Symbology, styling and presentation of geospatial features.
- Metadata & Quality
 - ISO 19115, 19115-2, 19157 – Ensure that datasets used within the mission-planning platform carry traceable provenance, quality and lineage.
- Operational Information Exchange
 - EDXL-SitRep (Situation Report) – Reporting operational statuses.
 - EDXL-CAP (Common Alerting Protocol) – Standardising alerting messages.
 - EDXL-RM (Resource Messaging) – Coordination of assets and response units.
- Emerging Work Items
 - OGC Testbeds focusing on federated mission-planning, cross-domain data exchange and streaming geospatial data.
 - ISO/TC 211 work on next-generation service interoperability and real-time geospatial APIs.
 - CEN/TC 391 initiatives related to crisis information models and interoperability in security operations.

These emerging efforts align closely with BorderForce’s objectives for a unified, collaborative, multi-user platform.

Gaps and Needs for New Standardisation Efforts

Although many standards exist for geospatial and emergency information systems, gaps remain in areas directly relevant to BorderForce:

1. Integration of Multimodal Fusion Outputs into GIS. OGC and ISO metadata frameworks are not fully equipped for:
 - a. Uncertainty and confidence annotation of fused intelligence,
 - b. Real-time sensor–fusion overlays,
 - c. Visualisation of AI-derived risk indicators.
2. Collaborative Mission-Planning Requirements. Existing standards do not define:
 - a. Multi-user editing of operational layers,
 - b. Real-time synchronisation of mission updates,
 - c. Shared annotations,
 - d. Role-based access control in collaborative GIS environments.
3. Border-Specific Operational Models. There is no standard framework describing:
 - a. Patrol routes,
 - b. Screening checkpoints,
 - c. Border-crossing risk indicators,
 - d. Fusion of EO/UAV/sensor data for border-related decision making.
4. Integration with XR and Advanced Visualisation. While XR has its own standards ecosystem, no bridging standards define how geospatial mission-planning content should be transferred into XR/MR environments.
5. Secure and Auditable Mission Workflows. Existing crisis management standards do not fully address:
 - a. Security requirements for collaborative map editing,
 - b. Provenance of operator edits,
 - c. Data integrity in adversarial settings,
 - d. Audit trails for mission decisions.
6. Offline and Low-Connectivity Operational Modes. Standard web services assume continuous connectivity; however, BorderForce operations often occur in:
 - a. Remote areas with no persistent networks,
 - b. Environments requiring offline caching,
 - c. Intermittent synchronisation modes.

These gaps are critical challenges and opportunities for innovation.

Potential BorderForce Contributions

BorderForce can significantly support and influence standardisation across multiple areas:

1. GIS Ontology and Data Models for Border Operations. BorderForce can propose:

- a. A structured ontology for border-security mission planning,
- b. Standardised feature types (patrol sector, illegal crossing point, risk hotspot, asset deployment area),
- c. Symbology and portrayal rules.

This could take the form of:

- d. An OGC Best Practice,
- e. A CEN/TR (Technical Report), or
- f. A future ISO Technical Specification.

2. Fusion-Aware Geospatial Data Structures. BorderForce can help define:

- a. Representations for fused sensor inputs,
- b. Risk layers derived from multimodal analytics,
- c. Mapped explainability annotations for AI-driven indicators.

These contributions align strongly with ongoing OGC Testbed activities.

3. Collaborative Editing & Multi-User Synchronisation Standards. Based on the field trials, BorderForce can offer guidance on:

- a. Operational requirements for collaborative GIS,
- b. Conflict resolution,
- c. Synchronised mission updates,
- d. Multi-role access control.

These insights can support new OGC or CEN work items.

4. Secure and Auditable Mission-Planning Workflows. BorderForce can propose:

- a. Methods for audit trails,
- b. Data signing,
- c. Operator identity management,
- d. Change provenance of mission layers.

These contributions align with CEN/CLC JTC 13 and ISO/IEC 270xx work.

5. Bridging GIS and XR Standards. By integrating XR tools with the mission-planning system, BorderForce can propose:

- a. Data transformation workflows,
- b. Symbology extensions for XR,
- c. Guidelines for immersive mission management.

This can support joint activities across OGC, ETSI ARF, ISO SC24 and Khronos/Metaverse initiatives.

6. Offline-Capable Mission Planning Guidance. BorderForce field trials will produce evidence for:
 - a. Caching mechanisms,
 - b. Offline map packages,
 - c. Degraded-mode operational procedures,
 - d. Synchronisation models for tactical deployments.

These contributions are highly valuable for standards that support real operational security missions.

6.4 GAP Analysis and Opportunities for New Contributions

This section synthesises the gaps identified across the standardisation landscape for all major BorderForce technology areas (T3.1–T3.4 and T4.1–T4.4) and outlines the strategic opportunities for the consortium to contribute to international, European and domain-specific standardisation efforts. The analysis draws from the Standardisation Roadmap, the technical descriptions of each subsystem, and the operational requirements defined in the Grant Agreement.

The objective of this gap analysis is twofold:

1. To identify where existing standards are insufficient, incomplete or absent, particularly in the context of integrated border surveillance, multimodal fusion, and AI-based decision support; and
2. To highlight opportunities for BorderForce to provide contributions, ranging from technical feedback and use-case descriptions to participation in working groups, drafting of best-practice documents and initiation of new standardisation efforts.

The gaps and opportunities identified here serve as a foundation for the Standardisation Roadmap, where specific timelines, responsibilities and milestones are presented.

6.4.1 Cross-Cutting Gaps Across All BorderForce Technologies

A number of systemic gaps span multiple technology areas, reflecting emerging domains where international standards have yet to mature.

Limited standards for integrated, multi-domain border surveillance ecosystems

1. Although individual domains—such as UAS operations, geospatial data, IoT sensors, or AI—are well covered by existing standards, there is no unified framework that integrates:
 - a. Satellite, drone and terrestrial sensors;
 - b. Multimodal AI fusion outputs;
 - c. C2 and mission planning interfaces;

- d. XR-based situational awareness;
- e. Federated sensor registries within tactical deployments.

This creates a significant interoperability challenge for border authorities and represents a key area where BorderForce can provide leadership.

2. Absence of standards linking AI fusion engines to operational decision-making. While AI ethics and risk management standards are rapidly evolving (ISO/IEC SC42, CEN-CLC JTC 21, ETSI SAI), few—if any—standards define:
 - a. How fused intelligence should be structured and communicated,
 - b. How uncertainty and confidence should be represented,
 - c. How automated risk indicators align with practitioner frameworks such as CIRAM.

BorderForce's multimodal fusion engine can supply valuable practical models for standardisation.

3. No standards for operational XR/MR in security missions. Existing XR standards focus on consumer or industrial applications. There is a gap in:
 - a. Mission-critical immersive interfaces,
 - b. Visualisation of live intelligence feeds,
 - c. Safety and operational constraints for XR use in field missions,
 - d. Interoperability between XR tools and C2 systems.

This presents a unique contribution pathway for the consortium.

4. Lack of interoperability profiles for mobile, deployable C2 units. Deployable C2 infrastructure, including sensor towers and UAV docking stations, is not covered by existing standards. No unified profile exists for:
 - a. Ad hoc C2 deployments in remote environments,
 - b. Integration with multi-hop mesh networks,
 - c. Field conditions such as limited power or degraded connectivity.

BorderForce's C2 prototype can inform such profiles.

5. Fragmented security and data-provenance requirements across components. Security and privacy standards exist for individual domains (e.g., AI, IoT, networks), but there is no overarching standard covering:
 - a. Provenance in multimodal intelligence systems,
 - b. Cross-border information-sharing under EU data protection principles,
 - c. Secure auditing of mission planning and intelligence dissemination workflows.

This gap is essential for future operational certification.

6.4.2 Gaps by Technology Area

Mobile C2 Station (T3.1)

- No standard model for deploying modular, portable C2 systems in border environments.
- Lack of c-UAS interoperability standards linking detection systems to C2 nodes.
- Insufficient requirements for edge-based multi-sensor fusion at the C2 station.

OSINT Toolkit (T3.2)

- No operational standards for real-time OSINT ingestion in security missions.
- Lack of benchmarks for misinformation/deepfake detection.
- Missing ethical and legal frameworks for OSINT in EU law enforcement.

Satellite-Drone Sensing & Swarm Intelligence (T3.3)

- No standards for joint UAV-satellite fusion workflows.
- Absence of multi-UAV coordination and swarm interoperability standards.
- Missing frameworks for AI-powered edge processing on aerial platforms.

Sensor Registry & External Data Integration (T3.4)

- Lack of unified metadata models for mixed aerial, terrestrial and space sensors.
- Limited standards for dynamic sensor onboarding/offboarding in tactical scenarios.
- No fusion-ready schemas for real-time intelligence workflows.

Multimodal Fusion & Risk Assessment (T4.1)

- No standardised schema for cross-modal fusion and uncertainty propagation.
- No operational explainability model tailored to border security risk scoring.
- No standard linking CIRAM principles to AI-driven risk assessment tools.

Mesh Communications Network (T4.2)

- Lack of standards for UAV-assisted mesh networking.
- No resilience models for mesh networks in contested border environments.
- Missing QoS and latency standards for AI-driven real-time intelligence pipelines.

XR/MR Situational Awareness Tools (T4.3)

- No XR standards for security-critical missions with live sensor overlays.
- Lack of safety and ergonomic guidelines for outdoor XR in extreme environments.
- No interoperability framework linking XR interfaces with geospatial platforms and C2 systems.

GIS-Based Mission Planning Platform (T4.4)

- No standard geospatial ontology for border operations, patrol sectors, risk zones or illegal-crossing indicators.
- No standards for collaborative, multi-user mission planning in security contexts.
- Lack of secure auditability standards for mission-plan modifications.

6.4.3 Opportunities for BorderForce Contributions

BorderForce is uniquely positioned to shape emerging standards due to the project's multi-domain innovations, real-world field trials, and integration of next-generation technologies. Key contribution opportunities include:

1. Development of new CEN Workshop Agreements (CWAs). Potential CWAs include:
 - a. Interoperability Profiles for Deployable C2 Stations and Multi-Sensor Surveillance Nodes
 - b. Guidelines for Federated Sensor Registries in Security Operations
 - c. OSINT Best Practices for Border-Security Intelligence
 - d. Multimodal Fusion and Explainability Models for Operational AI Systems
 - e. XR Interaction Guidelines for High-Stakes, Field-Based Missions

CWAs represent flexible, fast-track opportunities for BorderForce to influence European standardisation.
2. Contributions to ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 42 on AI Standards. BorderForce can offer:
 - a. Real-world datasets for transparency and explainability work items,
 - b. Lessons learned from AI governance in operational risk scoring,
 - c. Fusion-specific metadata and uncertainty modelling approaches.
3. Participation in OGC Testbeds and Standard Working Groups. BorderForce can propose:
 - a. A UAV-Satellite Fusion Profile,
 - b. New geospatial symbologies for border operations,
 - c. Extensions to OGC SensorThings and O&M for high-frequency and multi-domain observations,
 - d. Enhanced requirements for OGC API Processes in mission planning and real-time reasoning.
4. Engagement with ETSI ISG ARF and ETSI SAI. Opportunities include:
 - a. Use cases for XR in mission-critical environments,
 - b. Security requirements for AI-enabled intelligence systems,

- c. Contributions to edge AI and resilience in contested networks.
5. Collaborative work with ISO/TC 20/SC 14/WG 8 and ISO/TC 20/SC 16. BorderForce can shape:
 - a. Downstream EO services for security intelligence,
 - b. UAV operational envelopes in multi-sensor operations,
 - c. Preliminary frameworks for multi-UAV coordination.
6. Proposing new technical reports or best practices. BorderForce may contribute to:
 - a. TR: Multimodal Intelligence Fusion for Border Security,
 - b. TR: Secure, Resilient Mesh Networks for Tactical Deployments,
 - c. BP: GIS-Based Mission Planning for Security & Border Management,
 - d. BP: AI-Assisted Risk Assessment in Operational Contexts.

These deliverables help inform emerging standards even when formal standardisation pathways are not yet established.

6.5 Risk Assessment for Standardisation Activities

This section identifies, assesses, and proposes mitigation measures for risks associated with achieving the project's standardisation objectives. Standardisation activities in BorderForce involve external dependencies (e.g., access to working groups, evolving priorities within SDOs), internal constraints (e.g., resource allocation, partner expertise), and uncertainties surrounding emerging technologies (e.g., AI, XR, swarm intelligence). As a result, proactive risk management is essential to ensure that BorderForce's contributions are feasible, timely, and aligned with relevant SDO agendas.

The risks described here are specific to standardisation engagement, contribution development, and adoption of standards across BorderForce technologies, complementing the technical and operational risk assessments of the overarching project.

6.5.1 Methodology

The risk assessment follows the Horizon Europe standard approach:

1. Identification of potential risks that may affect standardisation outcomes.
2. Analysis of the likelihood (L) and impact (I) on a scale of Low (1), Medium (2), High (3).
3. Evaluation of risk levels based on $L \times I$.
4. Mitigation strategies assigned to responsible partners.
5. Monitoring through the WP6 Standardisation Monitoring Framework.

Risks are grouped into categories:

1. External SDO-related risks,

2. Internal coordination risks,
3. Technical maturity risks,
4. Regulatory and interoperability alignment risks.

6.5.2 Risk Register for Standardisation Activities

The following table summarises the key risks. (A formatted table will be included in the final deliverable.)

Risk 1 – Limited Access to Relevant SDO Working Groups

Description: Some SDO WGs (e.g., ISO/IEC SC42 AI subgroups, IEEE committees, certain OGC pilot groups) have restricted membership, require fees, or limit participation to selected experts. This may hinder timely engagement.

Likelihood: Medium (2)

Impact: High (3)

Mitigation:

- Use National Mirror Committees to participate indirectly.
- Leverage existing memberships held by consortium partners (e.g., GSH, VTT, ED, Eticas).
- Submit written contributions even without voting rights.
- Coordinate with other EU-funded projects to jointly access closed groups.

Risk 2 – Misalignment Between BorderForce Timelines and SDO Roadmaps

Description: SDOs follow their own schedules; draft standards may not be open for comments during BorderForce’s active periods.

Likelihood: High (3)

Impact: Medium (2)

Mitigation:

- Maintain continuous monitoring through quarterly reports (WP6).
- Prioritise contributions to fast-track processes (e.g., CWAs, OGC Best Practices).
- Disseminate project outputs through white papers if formal standardisation windows do not align.

Risk 3 – Insufficient Partner Capacity or Expertise for Sustained Engagement

Description: Standardisation work requires specialised expertise, time, and continuity, which may be challenging for partners during peak project phases.

Likelihood: Medium (2)

Impact: Medium (2)

Mitigation:

- Assign backup partners for each SDO WG (as per Section 7.3's matrix).
- Provide internal guidance and training on standardisation processes.
- Focus on targeted contributions where BorderForce adds the most value.

Risk 4 – Rapid Evolution of AI, XR, and Multi-Sensor Standards

Description: Emerging domains such as trustworthy AI, XR in mission-critical environments, and swarm intelligence evolve quickly, risking obsolescence of planned contributions.

Likelihood: High (3)

Impact: Medium (2)

Mitigation:

- Adopt a living-roadmap approach updated annually.
- Prioritise contributions to emerging work items, not established standards.
- Ensure flexibility in deliverables to incorporate new findings (e.g., field-trial evidence).

Risk 5 – Fragmentation of Standards Across Domains

Description: BorderForce combines space, drone, AI, IoT, GIS, mesh networks, and XR—domains where standards are siloed. This fragmentation may limit integrated standardisation contribution opportunities.

Likelihood: Medium (2)

Impact: High (3)

Mitigation:

- Promote cross-domain contributions (e.g., multimodal fusion data schemas).
- Engage with SDOs known for interoperability frameworks (OGC, CEN/TC 391).
- Draft internal harmonisation templates early (T3–T4 collaboration).

Risk 6 – Low Adoption of Proposed Standardisation Outputs

Description: Contributions such as CWAs or Best Practices may see limited uptake if not aligned with practitioner needs.

Likelihood: Low–Medium (1–2)

Impact: High (3)

Mitigation:

- Integrate end-user feedback from WP5 field trials.

- Present outputs at security practitioner networks (e.g., ENLETS, CERIS).
- Align contributions directly with capability gaps in Member States.

Risk 7 – Data Protection and Ethical Constraints Impacting Standardisation Outputs

Description: Standardisation proposals involving AI, OSINT, or situational awareness must respect GDPR, national legislation, and ethical limitations, which may restrict the dissemination of examples or datasets.

Likelihood: Medium (2)

Impact: High (3)

Mitigation:

- Include Eticas and legal partners early in drafting.
- Use synthetic or redacted datasets in contributions.
- Align with CEN-CLC JTC 21 and ETSI SAI guidance on privacy-preserving AI.

Risk 8 – Limited Evidence from Field Trials to Support Standardisation Contributions

Description: If field trials in WP5 experience delays or reduced operational scope, the ability to validate real-world use cases for standardisation may be reduced.

Likelihood: Medium (2)

Impact: Medium–High (2–3)

Mitigation:

- Use simulated testbeds or lab deployments as fallback evidence sources.
- Prepare draft contributions independent of field-trial timing.
- Coordinate early with end-user partners on trial design.

Risk 9 – Dependence on External Vendors for Hardware/Software Standards Compliance

Description: Some subsystems rely on third-party hardware or software (e.g., UAV components, XR headsets), which may not fully support the standards required for contribution.

Likelihood: Medium (2)

Impact: Medium (2)

- Mitigation:
- Select vendor solutions with established standards alignment (OpenXR, OGC APIs).
- Maintain modular interfaces that allow swapping components.
- Document vendor limitations explicitly in roadmap updates.

6.5.3 Risk Monitoring and Governance Mechanisms

Standardisation risks are monitored through three mechanisms:

1. WP6 Standardisation Steering Group

A dedicated internal task force monitors risk levels, provides monthly updates to the WP6 leader, and ensures alignment across WPs.

2. Quarterly Reporting Framework

Each partner submits contributions, risk updates, and mitigation actions as part of WP6's monitoring process. Risks are reassessed quarterly and escalated if needed.

3. Annual Roadmap Revisions (M12 and M24)

Based on evolving SDO agendas, new opportunities or emerging risks, the roadmap is updated twice during the project. Risk ratings are adjusted accordingly.

7 CONCLUSIONS

BorderForce is a significant project that tackles key challenges and upholds core principles central to the EU's societal values. Its vision places citizens at the centre, seeking to improve everyday life by enhancing security and providing effective support to Border Force authorities.

Deliverable D6.2 has provided a comprehensive overview of the communication, dissemination, and Advisory Board activities conducted during the first project period (M1 – M15), as well as an outline of the exploitation and standardisation plans for the BorderForce project. The deliverable demonstrates that the planned actions have been effectively implemented, building upon the Initial Communication and Dissemination Plan established in Month 3.

Communication and dissemination activities have ensured high visibility of the project among target stakeholders, including border authorities, policy makers, and the wider public. The Advisory Board and external stakeholder engagement has provided valuable feedback, fostering collaboration and alignment with user needs and operational requirements.

The exploitation plan identifies key exploitable results, potential end-users, market opportunities, and preliminary routes to market, providing a solid basis for further development and uptake of BorderForce outcomes. Similarly, the standardisation plan outlines objectives, methodology, and opportunities for contributions to relevant standards, ensuring that the project results are aligned with current and emerging frameworks.

Overall, D6.2 confirms that WP6 objectives are on track and sets the foundation for the next project phase (M16–M30), where communication, dissemination, exploitation and standardisation activities will be further consolidated and expanded to maximise impact, sustainability and adoption of BorderForce results.

ANNEX

List of Dissemination and Communication Activities performed during M1-M15

Partner	Type of Activity	Description (title of event, main content of message, etc.)	Evidence Kept/URL (if applicable)	Date [YYYY.MM.D]
ALL	Article/Post on BorderForce Website	BorderForce kickoff meeting at Vienna	https://borderforce-horizon.eu/2024/11/28/kickoff-meeting-at-vienna/	2024.11.28
ALL	Article/Post on BorderForce Website	Study visit to Lithuania 2025	https://borderforce-horizon.eu/2025/01/09/study-visit-to-lithuania-2025/	2025.01.09
ALL	Article/Post on BorderForce Website	Study visit to Bulgaria April 2025	https://borderforce-horizon.eu/2025/04/30/study-visit-to-bulgaria-april-2025/	2025.04.30
ALL	Article/Post on BorderForce Website	Successful 1st Consortium Meeting of the BorderForce Project Held in Tampere, Finland	https://borderforce-horizon.eu/2025/06/18/successful-1st-consortium-meeting-of-the-borderforce-project-held-in-tampere-finland/	2025.06.18
ALL	Article/Post on BorderForce Website	BorderForce System successfully tested at Securiton GmbH	https://borderforce-horizon.eu/2025/12/16/borderforce-system-successfully-tested-at-securiton-gmbh/	2025.12.16
ALL	Article/Post on BorderForce Social media (LinkedIn)	Easter Wishes	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7317875775326576641	2025.04.15
ALL	Article/Post on BorderForce Social media (LinkedIn)	BorderForce Study visit in Bulgaria	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7327633582582030336	2025.05.12
ALL	Article/Post on BorderForce Social media (LinkedIn)	BorderForce 1st Consortium Meeting	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7340745128002686981	2025.06.17
ALL	Article/Post on BorderForce Social media (LinkedIn)	BorderForce Summer holidays wishes	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7358859260090376193	2025.08.06
ALL	Article/Post on BorderForce Social media (LinkedIn)	The Floor to the Partners - VTT	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7393619364073324546	2025.11.10
ALL	Article/Post on BorderForce Social media (LinkedIn)	Announcement of Securiton GMBH Industrial tests	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7397232654040875008	2025.11.20

ALL	Article/Post on BorderForce Social media (LinkedIn)	First day at Securiton GMBH Industrial tests	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7398706996516032512	2025.11.24
ALL	Article/Post on BorderForce Social media (LinkedIn)	Second day at Securiton GMBH Industrial tests	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7399107489809702912	2025.11.25
ALL	Article/Post on BorderForce Social media (LinkedIn)	Third day at Securiton GMBH Industrial tests	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7399457286752108544	2025.11.26
ALL	Article/Post on BorderForce Social media (LinkedIn)	Fourth day at Securiton GMBH Industrial tests	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7399825794203639808	2025.11.27
ALL	Article/Post on BorderForce Social media (LinkedIn)	Fifth day at Securiton GMBH Industrial tests	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7400181556193079298	2025.11.28
ALL	Article/Post on BorderForce Social media (LinkedIn)	The Floor to the Partners - Securiton GMBH	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7404508030694023168	2025.12.10
ALL	Article/Post on BorderForce Social media (LinkedIn)	Successful completion of industrial test at Securiton GMBH	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7407124231584382976	2025.12.17
ALL	Article/Post on BorderForce Social media (LinkedIn)	Season's Greetings from BorderForce	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7408778325051052034	2025.12.22
ALL	Article/Post on BorderForce Social media (X)	BorderForce kickoff meeting at Vienna	https://x.com/BorderForce_/status/1865453423404949904?s=20	2024.12.07
ALL	Article/Post on BorderForce Social media (X)	Season's Greetings from BorderForce	https://x.com/BorderForce_/status/1869011036860559493?s=20	2024.12.17
ALL	Article/Post on BorderForce Social media (X)	BorderForce Study visit in Lithuania	https://x.com/BorderForce_/status/1890037164295225766?s=20	2025.02.13
ALL	Article/Post on BorderForce Social media (X)	International Women's Day	https://x.com/BorderForce_/status/1898112811059847369?s=20	2025.03.07

ALL	Article/Post on BorderForce Social media (X)	Easter Wishes	https://x.com/BorderForce_/status/1912108406749507619?s=20	2025.04.15
ALL	Article/Post on BorderForce Social media (X)	BorderForce Study visit in Bulgaria	https://x.com/BorderForce_/status/1921878578674696657?s=20	2025.05.12
ALL	Article/Post on BorderForce Social media (X)	BorderForce 1st Consortium Meeting	https://x.com/BorderForce_/status/1942494129608372379?s=20	2025.07.08
ALL	Article/Post on BorderForce Social media (Instagram)	BorderForce logo	https://www.instagram.com/p/DB_bH-dtbq4/?utm_source=ig_web_copy_link&igsh=MzRIODBiNWFIZA==	2024.11.05
ALL	Article/Post on BorderForce Social media (Instagram)	BorderForce logo & EU Horizon funding	https://www.instagram.com/p/DB_bsbSNJ3q/?utm_source=ig_web_copy_link&igsh=MzRIODBiNWFIZA==	2024.11.05
ALL	Article/Post on BorderForce Social media (Instagram)	BorderForce logo black	https://www.instagram.com/p/DB_bvAdN_fy/?utm_source=ig_web_copy_link&igsh=MzRIODBiNWFIZA==	2024.11.05
ALL	Article/Post on BorderForce Social media (Instagram)	BorderForce kickoff meeting at Vienna	https://www.instagram.com/p/DDSSBg0tnw9/?utm_source=ig_web_copy_link&igsh=MzRIODBiNWFIZA==	2024.12.07
ALL	Article/Post on BorderForce Social media (Instagram)	BorderForce kickoff meeting at Vienna	https://www.instagram.com/p/DDSSIUZN8-L/?utm_source=ig_web_copy_link&igsh=MzRIODBiNWFIZA==	2024.12.07
ALL	Article/Post on BorderForce Social media (Instagram)	Season's Greetings from BorderForce	https://www.instagram.com/p/DDrmFPAN_Ar/?utm_source=ig_web_copy_link&igsh=MzRIODBiNWFIZA==	2024.12.17
ALL	Article/Post on BorderForce Social media (Instagram)	BorderForce Study visit in Lithuania	https://www.instagram.com/p/DGBC2p_tgP0/?utm_source=ig_web_copy_link&igsh=MzRIODBiNWFIZA==	2025.02.13
ALL	Article/Post on BorderForce Social media (Instagram)	International Women's Day	https://www.instagram.com/p/DG6XwePNR51/?utm_source=ig_web_copy_link&igsh=MzRIODBiNWFIZA==	2025.03.07
ALL	Article/Post on BorderForce Social media (Instagram)	Easter Wishes	https://www.instagram.com/p/DldzO1rNZ2T/?utm_source=ig_web_copy_link&igsh=MzRIODBiNWFIZA==	2025.04.15

ALL	Article/Post on BorderForce Social media (Instagram)	BorderForce Study visit in Bulgaria	https://www.instagram.com/p/DJj13hftTAd/?utm_source=ig_web_copy_link&igsh=MzRIODBiNWFIZA==	2025.05.12
ALL	Article/Post on BorderForce Social media (Instagram)	BorderForce EU Horizon funding	https://www.instagram.com/p/DJnvN3Wls6q/?utm_source=ig_web_copy_link&igsh=MzRIODBiNWFIZA==	2025.05.14
ALL	Article/Post on BorderForce Social media (Instagram)	BorderForce Summer holidays wishes	https://www.instagram.com/p/DNBCbIFtpub/?utm_source=ig_web_copy_link&igsh=MzRIODBiNWFIZA==	2025.08.06
ALL	Article/Post on BorderForce Social media (Instagram)	The Floor to the Partners - VTT	https://www.instagram.com/p/DQ4GgLrjRKq/?utm_source=ig_web_copy_link&igsh=MzRIODBiNWFIZA==	2025.11.10
ALL	Article/Post on BorderForce Social media (Instagram)	Announcement of Securiton GMBH Industrial tests	https://www.instagram.com/p/DRRsf3ZDakF/?utm_source=ig_web_copy_link&igsh=MzRIODBiNWFIZA==	2025.11.20
ALL	Article/Post on BorderForce Social media (Instagram)	First day at Securiton GMBH Industrial tests	https://www.instagram.com/p/DRcKwPEJTFU/?utm_source=ig_web_copy_link&igsh=MzRIODBiNWFIZA==	2025.11.24
ALL	Article/Post on BorderForce Social media (Instagram)	Second day at Securiton GMBH Industrial tests	https://www.instagram.com/p/DRfA05SCGDV/?utm_source=ig_web_copy_link&igsh=MzRIODBiNWFIZA==	2025.11.25
ALL	Article/Post on BorderForce Social media (Instagram)	Third day at Securiton GMBH Industrial tests	https://www.instagram.com/p/DRhgAQzCGrB/?utm_source=ig_web_copy_link&igsh=MzRIODBiNWFIZA==	2025.11.26
ALL	Article/Post on BorderForce Social media (Instagram)	Fourth day at Securiton GMBH Industrial tests	https://www.instagram.com/p/DRkHomkCAHS/?utm_source=ig_web_copy_link&igsh=MzRIODBiNWFIZA==	2025.11.27
ALL	Article/Post on BorderForce Social media (Instagram)	Fifth day at Securiton GMBH Industrial tests	https://www.instagram.com/p/DRmpbJICl8s/?utm_source=ig_web_copy_link&igsh=MzRIODBiNWFIZA==	2025.11.28
ALL	Article/Post on BorderForce Social media (Instagram)	The Floor to the Partners - Securiton GMBH	https://www.instagram.com/p/DSFY3-kDTt/?utm_source=ig_web_copy_link&igsh=MzRIODBiNWFIZA==	2025.12.10
ALL	Article/Post on BorderForce Social media (Instagram)	Season's Greetings from BorderForce	https://www.instagram.com/p/DSkPxeDXDM/?utm_source=ig_web_copy_link&igsh=MzRIODBiNWFIZA==	2025.12.22

ALL	Article/Post on BorderForce Social media (Facebook)	BorderForce logo	https://www.facebook.com/photo?fbid=122106571160593671&set=pb.61567810143901.-2207520000	2024.11.05
ALL	Article/Post on BorderForce Social media (Facebook)	BorderForce logo & EU Horizon funding	https://www.facebook.com/photo?fbid=122106577064593671&set=pb.61567810143901.-2207520000	2024.11.05
ALL	Article/Post on BorderForce Social media (Facebook)	BorderForce kickoff meeting at Vienna	https://www.facebook.com/photo?fbid=122116157414593671&set=pb.61567810143901.-2207520000	2024.12.07
ALL	Article/Post on BorderForce Social media (Facebook)	BorderForce kickoff meeting at Vienna	https://www.facebook.com/photo?fbid=122116157486593671&set=pb.61567810143901.-2207520000	2024.12.07
ALL	Article/Post on BorderForce Social media (Facebook)	Season’s Greetings from BorderForce	https://www.facebook.com/photo?fbid=122118031574593671&set=pb.61567810143901.-2207520000	2024.12.17
ALL	Article/Post on BorderForce Social media (Facebook)	BorderForce Study visit in Lithuania	https://www.facebook.com/share/p/14QxbWURfg7/?mibextid=wwXlfr	2025.02.13
ALL	Article/Post on BorderForce Social media (Facebook)	BorderForce Study visit in Lithuania	https://www.facebook.com/share/p/198bCKF2hQ/?mibextid=wwXlfr	2025.02.13
ALL	Article/Post on BorderForce Social media (Facebook)	International Women’s Day	https://www.facebook.com/share/p/1BcK1TAS5s/?mibextid=wwXlfr	2025.03.07
ALL	Article/Post on BorderForce Social media (Facebook)	Easter Wishes	https://www.facebook.com/share/p/1Bwx8ehEmp/?mibextid=wwXlfr	2025.04.15
ALL	Article/Post on BorderForce Social media (Facebook)	BorderForce Study visit in Bulgaria	https://www.facebook.com/share/p/17cKFZPnwx/?mibextid=wwXlfr	2025.05.12
ALL	Article/Post on BorderForce Social media (Facebook)	BorderForce EU Horizon funding	https://www.facebook.com/share/1AZXEh7xNx/?mibextid=wwXlfr	2025.05.14
ALL	Article/Post on BorderForce Social media (Facebook)	BorderForce 1st Consortium Meeting	https://www.facebook.com/share/p/1ByuaAuvGa/?mibextid=wwXlfr	2025.06.18

ALL	Article/Post on BorderForce Social media (Facebook)	BorderForce Summer holidays wishes	https://www.facebook.com/share/p/14R8PG7kp1A/?mibextid=wwXlfr	2025.08.06
ALL	Article/Post on BorderForce Social media (Facebook)	The Floor to the Partners - VTT	https://www.facebook.com/share/p/17ak5vkWt8/?mibextid=wwXlfr	2025.11.10
ALL	Article/Post on BorderForce Social media (Facebook)	Announcement of Securiton GMBH Industrial tests	https://www.facebook.com/share/p/1DN G2gJN6e/?mibextid=wwXlfr	2025.11.20
ALL	Article/Post on BorderForce Social media (Facebook)	First day at Securiton GMBH Industrial tests	https://www.facebook.com/share/p/1CH uk6r1wt/?mibextid=wwXlfr	2025.11.24
ALL	Article/Post on BorderForce Social media (Facebook)	Second day at Securiton GMBH Industrial tests	https://www.facebook.com/share/p/17E QJk86E/?mibextid=wwXlfr	2025.11.25
ALL	Article/Post on BorderForce Social media (Facebook)	Third day at Securiton GMBH Industrial tests	https://www.facebook.com/share/p/187 QPpYhK2/?mibextid=wwXlfr	2025.11.26
ALL	Article/Post on BorderForce Social media (Facebook)	Fourth day at Securiton GMBH Industrial tests	https://www.facebook.com/share/p/1RT 1WdDPgB/?mibextid=wwXlfr	2025.11.27
ALL	Article/Post on BorderForce Social media (Facebook)	Fifth day at Securiton GMBH Industrial tests	https://www.facebook.com/share/p/1Eb AF8a7ff/?mibextid=wwXlfr	2025.11.28
ALL	Article/Post on BorderForce Social media (Facebook)	The Floor to the Partners - Securiton GMBH	https://www.facebook.com/share/p/1Ae uJg49gn/?mibextid=wwXlfr	2025.12.10
ALL	Article/Post on BorderForce Social media (Facebook)	Season's Greetings from BorderForce	https://www.facebook.com/share/p/1ET FjDuBAa/?mibextid=wwXlfr	2025.12.22

